

Original paper

Contribution to the flora of Velika plaža and its vicinity in Ulcinj (Montenegro)

Nada BUBANJA¹, Jasmina ŠINŽAR-SEKULIĆ², Vladimir STEVANOVIĆ²¹Natural History Museum of Montenegro, Trg Vojvode Bećir Bega Osmanagića 16, Podgorica, Montenegro,²Institute of Botany and Botanical Garden "Jevremovac", Belgrade, Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade, Takovska 43, Belgrade, Serbia

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Summary. This paper presents a taxonomic, ecological and phytogeographic study of the flora of the longest Adriatic beach - Velika plaža, its vicinity, and the island of Ada Bojana in Ulcinj. According to field research and a literature review, there are 962 taxa (species and subspecies) in the area of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana, which represents one fourth of the total Montenegrin flora. The family with the highest number of taxa is Poaceae, while the genus with the largest number of taxa is *Euphorbia*. Terophytes and hemicryptophytes are dominant in the biological spectrum. Chorological analysis has shown that the Mediterranean-Sub-Mediterranean areal type is the most prominent. There are 12 NATURA 2000 habitats and several associations that belong to a particular type of habitat within the area of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana. Endemic flora is represented by 16 species. Thirty-six relict species have been recorded, as well as 37 species under legal protection within the research area.

Keywords: ecological, flora, phytogeographic study, taxonomic, Velika plaža.

INTRODUCTION

Diversity and endemism centers of the vascular flora in Montenegro are high-mountain areas, and the presence of 1540 taxa certainly points to the great floristic diversity in the Mediterranean area of Montenegro (Caković and Milosevic 2103). Regarding the coastal region of Montenegro there are several botanically significant sites (Velika plaža, Tivatska solila, Ulcinjska Solana ...) that represent unique nature areas that are distinguished by a variety of plant species and communities, some of which are limited only to these areas.

Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana, due to the presence of psammo- halophytic vegetation that has existed there since ancient times, has attracted the attention of research botanists. From the first floristic data published by A. Baldacci in 1898 for Ulcinj and its surroundings (Pulević and Vinček 2004) until 2011 when our own research began, a considerable number of papers have been published containing information on the flora and vegetation of this area.

Research conducted by most botanists at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries (Baldacci 1891, 1898, 1900, 1910; Horak 1900; Rohlena 1902a, 1902b, 1904, 1942; Adamović 1913) was focused on the surroundings of Ulcinj. The largest number of floristic data for Ulcinj and its surroundings were provided by Josef Rohlena (Rohlena 1902a, 1902b, 1903, 1904, 1911, 1923, 1931, 1933, 1936, 1942) and Lujó Adamović (Adamović 1911, 1912a, 1912b, 1913). In the second half of the twentieth century and early XXI century, several botanists occasionally engaged in exploration of this area, with an emphasis on the flora and vegetation of the sandy Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana (Fukarek 1954; Janković and Bogojević 1965; Trinajstić 1989; Mijović 1994; Lakušić et al. 2004; Petrović and Vuksanović 2005; Mijović et al. 2006, 2012; Vuksanović and Petrović 2007; Bujanja and Stevanović 2013; Caković et al. 2013, 2014; Bujanja et al. 2016; Nobis et al. 2017; Stešević and Bujanja 2017; Stešević et al. 2017a, 2017b; Šilc et al. 2016, 2017). In

order to supplement literature and herbarium data on the taxonomic structure, distribution and diversity, phytogeographic and ecological characteristics, the degree of vulnerability and the possibility of protection of autochthonous flora in the area of Velika plaža and its vicinity and the island of Ada Bojana, detailed floristic research began in spring 2011. Given that this is an area with the best preserved psammohalophytic vegetation on the Montenegrin coast, and that it represents the last refugium of this type of vegetation in the Mediterranean region, as well as the fact that coastal wetland habitats in the Mediterranean are among the most important in terms of biodiversity preservation, attention was paid to the identification of NATURA 2000 habitat in accordance with the European Union habitat interpretation handbook (EUROPEAN COMMISSION DIRECTORATES GENERAL 2007), as well as with the Catalogue of habitat types of EU importance of Montenegro.

Study area

Ulcinj is the southernmost town in Montenegro, which is partly open to the Adriatic and Mediterranean Sea (Strait of Otranto), and its border with Albania runs along the Bojana River over a length of 24 km and then to the by land over a length of 7 km as the crow flies. Velika plaža is 5 km away from Ulcinj; it is about 13 km long and about 1.5 km wide; it is surrounded by the Porto Milena Channel on the west and the Bojana River on the east (Fig. 1). The altitude of the Velika plaža ranges from 0 to 5 m. At the mouth of the Bojana River there is the island of Ada with a surface of 450 ha; the length of the beach is 3.7 km and the altitude of the island ranges from 0 to 3 m (Perović 1988; Radojičić 2008a, 2008b). The total length of the Montenegrin coastline is 277.95 km including 32.70 km which belong to the area of Ulcinj, out of which almost 50% encompass Long Beach (Velika plaža) and the island of Ada Bojana.

Fig. 1. Research area of the flora of Velika plaža and its vicinity in Ulcinj (Montenegro).

Floristic research presented in this paper included Porto Milena Channel, a sandy beach with dunes and dry dune pastures, dry meadows, as well as salt marsh meadows with smaller and larger permanent and intermittent water basins, hydrophilic meadows and flooded forests in the vicinity of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana. The surface of the research area is about 1500 ha and includes Velika plaža over a length of 13 km and the island of Ada Bojana over a length of 3.7 km. The research area is composed of carbonate sedimentary rocks and clastic chalk rocks, from the tertiary and quaternary periods (Mirković et al. 1978). In the area of the Velika plaža, marine sand takes up to 600 ha, from the Channel Porto Milena canal to the mouth of the river Bojana, including the island of Ada Bojana. The width of the sandy belt is 250 - 500 m. From the sandy beach to the salt pans and the River Bojana there is the so-called Štojaska pješčana greda which consists of Brijeg mora (sand dunes on the beach) and Špatula, as well as the settlements Donji Štoj, Gornji Štoj and Sveti Nikola. Around the road Ulcinj - Bojana there is a little depression with a depth of 2.2 to 2.6 m. Between this depression and Velika plaža there are elevated terrains in Brijeg mora and Sveti Nikola with altitudes ranging from 3.2 to 4.4 m, but here there are also smaller depressions filled with water and swampy vegetation known as kneta. Apart from the sand there is also alluvial-colluvial (slightly water-logged and slightly salinized) eugley soil (Fušić and Đuretić 2000). The Mediterranean climate is typical for this region due to the proximity of the Mediterranean Sea, which is characterized by dry summers and mild winters (Perović 1988; Dömpke 2008).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research of the flora in the area of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana in Ulcinj was carried out over a period from 2011 to 2016. The collected herbal material was partially herbaceous. Collected materials were preserved in 60% alcohol and deposited in either the botanical collection of the Natural History Museum of Montenegro, and or the botanical garden of the Faculty of Biology in Belgrade (BEOU). For the purpose of determination of plant material several literature resources were used: Jávorka and Csapody (1934), Рбічин (1948), Tutin et al. (1964 - 1980, 2010), Josifović (ed) (1970 - 1977), Fiori and Paoletti (1970), Pignatti (1982), Šarić (1986), Sarić et al. (1986, 1992), Preston (1995) etc. The nomenclature was aligned with Flora Europea (Tutin et al 1964-1980), as well as the Med-Check list (Greuter et al. 1984, 1986, 1989). Floral elements were determined and analyzed in accordance with the principles of division of Meuselet al. (1965, 1978), Meusel et al. (1992), Pignatti (1982), Gajić (1980), Greuter et al. (1984, 1986, 1989), Med - Checklist (2007 -), and their classification into areal types areal groups

has been aligned with the phytogeographical classification of Stevanović (1995). In the classification of life forms, Raunkiaer division was applied (and was supplemented by Ellenberg and Mueller-Dombois (1967), while Stevanović (1992a, 1992b) was supplemented and corrected for our conditions). The NATURA 2000 habitat type is marked with a code and a name in accordance with the European Union habitat interpretation handbook (EUROPEAN COMMISSION DIRECTORATES GENERAL 2007), as well as with the Catalogue of habitat types of EU importance of Montenegro (Petrović et al. 2012). Environmental indices have been adopted from Pignatti (2005) and 7 indices have been taken into consideration: for light (L), temperature (T), continentality (C), humidity (U), substrate reaction (R), the amount of nitrogen (N) and salinity (S). In addition to each of the listed taxon (Appendix 1), the life form and its affiliation to a specific floral element has been provided as well. For specific taxa, their affiliation to plant associations and the NATURA 2000 habitat have also been included. The list also includes taxa found earlier at the same sites that the authors did not find during the present study. Such taxa are marked with an asterisk (*) next to their names, and in parentheses the name of the author and year of the reference when that taxon was mentioned is provided).

RESULTS

The list of plant species and subspecies for Velika plaža in Ulcinj and the island of Ada Bojana (Appendix 1) includes 962 taxa classified into 125 families and 516 genera. Poaceae with 99 species, Asteraceae with 85 species, Fabaceae with 79 species were found to be predominant in the taxonomic spectrum of families, while *Euphorbia* (2.1%) and *Trifolium* (1.9%) were dominant in the spectrum of genera. Detailed taxonomic spectra of families and genera are shown in Table 1.

The biological spectrum of Velika plaža and the Island of Ada Bojana is characterized by the dominance of terophytes (35.6%), while areal spectra of the total vascular flora of the research area suggest dominance of the Mediterranean-submediterranean areal type (38.1%), which can be explained by the geographic position of the research area: *i.e.* by the intrinsic influence of the Mediterranean climate. A detailed biological and horological spectrum is shown in Table 2, which shows that the participation of adventive flora in the total flora of the research area is non-negligible (10.5%). During our research of Velika plaža, three new taxa (belonging to the adventives flora) were identified within the flora of Montenegro - *Elodea canadensis* Michx., *Physalis angulata* L. and *Coreopsis tinctoria* Nutt.

Having analyzed the ecological indices of plants in the research area, it was found that in terms of light regime (L), semi-sciophytes with index values L7 and L8 were prevalent;

Table 1. Families and genera with the largest number of species and subspecies in the flora of Velika plaža and Ada Bojana.

Family	N°	%	Family	N°	%
Poaceae	99	10.3	Liliaceae	22	2.3
Asteraceae	85	9.0	Ranunculaceae	19	2.0
Fabaceae	79	8.2	Orchidaceae	17	1.8
Brassicaceae	42	4.4	Polygonaceae	14	1.5
Scrophulariaceae	34	3.6	Rosaceae	19	2.0
Lamiaceae	33	3.4	Rubiaceae	13	1.4
Cyperaceae	33	3.4	Juncaceae	13	1.4
Caryophylliaceae	31	3.2	Geraniaceae	12	1.2
Apiaceae	31	3.2	Goraginaceae	12	1.2
Chenopodiaceae	25	2.6	Solanaceae	11	1.1
Euphorbiaceae	22	2.3			
Genus	N°	%	Genus	N°	%
<i>Euphorbia</i>	20	2.1	<i>Geranium</i>	8	0.8
<i>Trifolium</i>	18	1.9	<i>Linum</i>	8	0.8
<i>Carex</i>	16	1.7	<i>Rumex</i>	8	0.8
<i>Veronica</i>	12	1.2	<i>Crepis</i>	7	0.7
<i>Medicago</i>	10	1.0	<i>Orchis</i>	7	0.7
<i>Juncus</i>	10	1.0	<i>Polygonum</i>	6	0.6
<i>Bromus</i>	10	1.0	<i>Vicia</i>	6	0.6
<i>Chenopodium</i>	9	0.9	<i>Verbascum</i>	6	0.6
<i>Silene</i>	9	0.9	<i>Plantago</i>	6	0.6
<i>Ranunculus</i>	8	0.8			

Table 2. Biological and Horological Spectrum in the flora of Velika plaža and Ada Bojana.

Life form	N°	%	Areal type	N°	%
Terophyta (T)	99	10.3	Holarctic	60	6.2
Hemicryptophyta (H)	85	9.0	Euroasian	198	20.6
Phanerophyta (P)	121	12.6	Middle south-eastern mountains	9	0.9
Geophyta (G)	106	11.0	Mediterranean-submediterranean	367	38.1
Hydrophyta (Hyd)	64	6.6	Mediterranean-pontic	75	7.8
Chamaephyta (Ch)	55	5.7	Central european- mediterranean	31	3.2
Scandetophyta (S)	28	2.9	Central european	14	1.5
Parasitophyta (Par)	5	0.5	Cosmopolitan	107	11.1
			Adventive	101	10.5

in terms of thermal regime of habitats (T), thermophile species with index values T7 and T8 were predominant; in terms of continentality (C), the species adapted to regions with temperate continental climate with index values C5 and C4 were predominant; in terms of humidity (U), mesophytes with index values U3 and U4 prevailed; in terms of substrate reaction (R), neutrophilic species with index value R5 were dominant; in terms of the amount of nitrogen in the soil

(N), oligotrophic species with index values N2 and N3 were prevalent; while in relation to salt tolerance in soil and water, (S) species tolerating lower salt concentration with index value S1, as well as species tolerating higher concentration of salt halophytes with index values S2 and S3 were dominant.

Different types of habitats can be found in the area of Velika plaža and Ada Bojana Island, resulting in a real vegetation "mosaic". Based on results from our field research

of the flora in this area, our observations and the available literature data, the presence of 12 NATURA 2000 habitats have been identified as well as several associations that belong to a particular type of a habitat. The present NATURA 2000 habitats are: 1310 *Salicornia* and other annuals colonising mud and sand, 1410 Mediterranean salt meadows (*Juncetalia maritimi*), 2110 Embryonic shifting dunes, 2120 Shifting dunes along the shoreline with *Ammophila arenaria* (white dunes), 2130* Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation (grey dunes), 2190 Humide dune slacks, 2220 Dunes with *Euphorbia terracina*, 2240 *Brachypodietalia* dune grasslands with annuals, 2270* Wooded dunes with *Pinus pinea* and/or *Pinus pinaster*, 3170* Mediterranean temporary ponds, 6420 Mediterranean tall humid herb grasslands of the *Molinio-Holoschoenion*, 92A0 *Salix alba* and *Populus alba* galleries. On the sandy beach, at the beginning of the coastal dunes (EU habitat 2110) the vegetation class CAKILETEA MARITIMAE (Tx. & Prsg) Br.-Bl. 1962 with the association *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae* (Beg. 1941) Pignatti 1953 are represented as well the vegetation class AMMOPHILETEA Br.-Bl. & Tx. 1943 with two associations *Agropyretum mediterraneum* (Kuhn.) Br. - Bl. 1933 and *Sporobolo-Elymetum farcti* (Gehu & al.) Gehu 1984, are represented on sand dunes. A vegetation class THEROBRACHYPODIETEA RAMOSI Br.-Bl. 1947 is represented on the dune pastures with one-year species of *Brachypodietalia* (EU habitat 2240). In the vicinity of the beach on salty

marsh meadows (EU habitat 1410), the presence of the vegetation class JUNCETEA MARITIMI Br.-Bl. 1931 was recorded, with associations *Juncetum maritimo-acuti* Horvatić 1934, *Eriantho-Schoenetum nigricantis* (Pignatti 1953) Géhu in Géhu et al. 1984, *Holoschoenetum romani* Tchou 1948. On marsh meadows in the vicinity of the beach there are sporadically emerging brackish and sweet water basins with lush emergent vegetation belonging to the class PHRAGMITIOMAGNOCARICETEA Klika in Klika & Novak 1941 with the association *Cladietum marisci* Allorge 1922 ex Zobrist 1935. In the south-eastern part of the vicinity of the beach and the island of Ada Bojana there are hygrophilous forests of the class QUERCETEA ROBORI-PETRAEA Br.-Bl. et Tx. 43 with the association *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis* Jank & Bogoj 1965 that belong to EU habitat 92A0.

Endemic flora of Velika plaža and the Island of Ada Bojana is represented with 16 species, of which 11 are endemic species and 5 sub-endemic species, whose distribution does not cross the borders of the Balkan region (see Table 3).

Thirty-six relict taxa have been recorded in the area of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana: *Butomus umbellatus*, *Campanula lingulata*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Castanea sativa*, *Celtis australis*, *Cionura erecta*, *Convolvulus cantabrica*, *Cotinus coggygria*, *Cydonia oblonga*, *Cynanchum acutum*, *Erythronium dens-canis*, *Ficus carica*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Hedera helix*, *Humulus lupulus*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Laurus nobilis*, *Lonicera caprifolium*, *Myrtus communis*, *Nerium oleander*,

Table 3. Endemics and subendemics in the flora of Velika plaža i Ada Bojana.

Endemic	Subendemic
<i>Chaerophyllum coloratum</i> L.	<i>Berteroa mutabilis</i> (Vent) DC.
<i>Colchicum cupanii</i> Guss. ssp. <i>glossophyllum</i> (Heldr.) Rouy	<i>Colchicum hungaricum</i> Janka
<i>Crocus dalmaticus</i> Vis.	<i>Crocus tommasinianus</i> Herbert
<i>Lysimachia atropurpurea</i> L.	<i>Iris pallida</i> Lam.
<i>Petrorhagia obcordata</i> (Margot & Reuter) Greuter & Burdet	<i>Limonium cancellatum</i> (Bernh ex Bertol) O. Kunntee
<i>Petteria ramentacea</i> (Sieber) C. Presl	
<i>Quercus robur</i> L. ssp. <i>scutariensis</i> Černjavski	
<i>Rhamnus intermedius</i> Stendel & Hochst	
<i>Sideritis romana</i> L. ssp. <i>purpurea</i> (Talbot ex Bentham) Heywood	
<i>Tanacetum cinerariifolium</i> (Trev.) Schultz Bip.	
<i>Vincetoxicum huteri</i> Vis. & Ascherson	

Olea europaea, *Ostrya carpinifolia*, *Osyris alba*, *Pancratium maritimum*, *Paliurus spina - christi*, *Periploca graeca*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *P. terebinthus*, *Rhus coriaria*, *Ruscus aculeatus*, *Salvia officinalis*, *Satureja montana*, *Smilax aspera*, *Tamus communis*, *Thelygonum cynocrambe*, *Vallisneria spiralis*. Thirty-seven taxa with national protection status (Službeni list RCG 2006): *Anacamptis pyramidalis*, *Aster tripolim*, *Cakile maritima*, *Calystegia soldanella*, *Chaerophyllum col-*

oratum, *Colchicum hungaricum*, *Echinophora spinosa*, *Eryngium maritimum*, *Euphorbia paralias*, *Galanthus nivalis*, *Hermodactylus tuberosus*, *Limonium angustifolium*, *Ophrys apifera*, *O. bertolonii*, *O. fusca*, *Orchis coriophora*, *O. italica*, *O. laxiflora*, *O. laxiflora* ssp. *palustris*, *O. morio* ssp. *morio*, *O. papilionacea*, *Pancratium maritimum*, *Polygonum maritimum*, *P. salicifolium*, *Posidonia oceanica*, *Quercus robur* ssp. *scutariensis*, *Rhamnus intermedius*, *Salicornia europaea*, *S.*

fruticosa, *Salsola kali*, *S. soda*, *Serapias cordigera*, *S. lingua*, *S. vomeracea*, *Spiranthes spiralis*, *Utricularia vulgaris*, *Vincetoxicum huteri*.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the present study, 962 taxa classified into 125 families and 516 genera have been registered in the area of Velika plaža and Ada Bojana Island. This great abundance of flora is a result of the geographic position of the research area, as well as geological, pedological, climate and anthropogenic influences. The most represented families are Poaceae and Asteraceae, which is as expected, both due to the open type of habitat present in the research area, and the fact that these two families are the most numerous in the Balkan region (Turrill 1929). In terms of grass, species characteristic of dry dune pastures and meadows are prevalent, while within the Asteraceae family ruderal plants are dominant. Concerning the taxonomic spectrum of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana, there is a significant presence of the families Fabaceae, Brassicaceae, Scrophulariaceae, Lamiaceae, Cyperaceae, Caryophyllaceae, Apiaceae, Chenopodiaceae, Euphorbiaceae. The genera *Euphorbia* and *Trifolium* are the most numerous, due to the intense anthropogenic impact in the area: species of these genera, that are otherwise ruderal representatives, are expected to be numerous within the research area. Genera *Carex*, *Veronica*, *Medicago*, *Juncus*, *Bromus* have a significant presence in the flora spectrum. The geographic position of the research area, *i.e.* the intense influence of the Mediterranean climate in the biological spectrum, has given rise to the dominance of terophytes (35.6%), which often occur in open and dry habitats within the area of Velika Plaža and the island of Ada Bojana. In addition, they are often found in habitats under anthropogenic influence, which is distinctive for this area. Phyto-geographic analysis showed the dominance of the Mediterranean-Sub-Mediterranean areal type (38.1%), which was also expected due to the geographic position of the research area, as well as the influence of the climate. Given the geographic position and climate of this area, which enables the cultivation of tropical species that are often planted by locals in their gardens and courtyards for decorative reasons, the presence of adventive flora (10.5%) within the research area is not negligible (Stešević and Petrović 2010; Stešević and Caković 2013; Stešević et al. 2017b). Regarding the flora of Montenegro, three adventive species have been recorded as novel: *Elodea canadensis* (Bubanja and Stevanović 2013), *Coreopsis tinctoria* and *Physalis angulata* (Stešević and Bubanja 2017). Analysis of environmental light indices indicates the dominance of semi-sciophytes, which is conditioned by the abundance of open and sunny habitats. Regarding the environmental temperature index, thermophilic species dominate, which

points to the Mediterranean character of this area, while with respect to the index of continentality, species adapted to areas with temperate continental climate prevail. In terms of the moisture index, mesophytes prevail, which is due to the large presence of moderately humid habitats in the vicinity of the beach. With reference to soil reaction, neutrophilic species are dominant, while in view of the presence of mineral matter in the soil oligotrophic species prevail. Regarding the salinity index, species that are tolerant to lower salt concentration are predominant. According to field research and observations of the flora in the area as well as based on the literature data, the presence of 12 NATURA habitats has been registered (EU habitats 1310, 1410, 2110, 2120, 2130*, 2190, 2220, 2240, 2270*, 3170*, 6420, 92A0) within the area of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana (Petrović et al. 2012). Later research on vegetation within the area of Velika plaža conducted by other researchers emphasizes that the presence of 2130* habitat is questionable for this site (Šilc et al. 2017). In Montenegro, five out of twelve of the above mentioned types of habitats have only been registered on Velika plaža and its vicinity so far: 2130* Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation (grey dunes), 2240 Brachypodietalia dune grasslands with annuals, 2270* Wooded dunes with *Pinus pinea* and/or *Pinus pinaster*, 3170* Mediterranean temporary ponds, 6420 Mediterranean tall humid herb grasslands of the *Molinio-Holoschoenion* (Caković and Milošević 2013). According to the literature data on vegetation within the area of Velika Plaža and the island of Ada Bojana, as well as based on our field observations, the presence of several plant communities has been recorded (*Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*, *Agropyretum mediterraneum*, *Sporobolo-Elymetum farcti*, *Juncetum maritimo-acuti*, *Eriantho-Schoenetum nigricantis*, *Holoschoenetum romani*, *Cladietum marisci*, *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*) (Adamović 1912a, 1912b; Horvatić 1963, 1974; Fukarek 1956; Janković and Bogojević 1965; Blečić and Lakušić 1976; Lakušić 1987; Trinajstić 1989; Mijović 1994, Mijović et al. 2006, 2012; Petrović et al. 2012). Later research on the flora and zoning of plant communities, which was carried out on the beach from the first colonizing plants across sandy dunes to forest vegetation, showed the presence of 9 plant communities (*Cakilo-Xanthietum italici*, *Cynodon dactylon* comm., *Euphorbio paraliae-Agropyretum junceiformis*, *Medicagini marinae-Ammophiletum australis*, *Onobrychis caput-galli* comm., *Cladietum marisci*, *Eriantho-Schoenetum nigricantis*, *Juncetum maritimo-acuti*, *Holoschoenetum romani*) (Stešević et al. 2017; Šilc et al. 2016, 2017). In this area, the presence of 16 endemic species, 36 relict species and 37 species protected by national legislation has been recorded (Turill 1929; Službeni list RCG 2006; Vuksanović 2016). Velika plaža, with all its natural value, has been recognized as a very important natural area for a long

time, and in 1968 was protected as a natural monument and included in the list of IPA areas (Službeni list SRCG 1968; Petrović and Karaman 2009). However, regardless of the fact that it is a protected area, the biggest danger to the flora and vegetation in the area of Velika plaža and its vicinity and the island of Ada Bojana remains to be anthropogenic factors (tourism and urbanization - construction of hotels, temporary beach facilities, camps, houses, sand exploitation, illegal disposal of solid waste, pasture, marine litter) which has been increasing in recent years (MonteCep 2007; Dömpke 2008; Šilc et al. 2017, 2018). In recent years, by enclosing the sand dunes in some parts of Velika plaža, additional measures for protection and preservation have been provided (Šilc et al. 2017). Therefore, Velika plaža and the Island of Ada Bojana with all their natural characteristics require a greater degree of protection to preserve these rare and unique habitats that are declining in almost the entire Mediterranean.

CONCLUSIONS

The floristic and vegetation diversity of Velika plaža and the island of Ada Bojana is large and unique in relation to all other beaches on the Montenegrin coast; this region has an extraordinary natural and landscape value, special attention should be given to provide more protection for this area in the future.

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Appendix 1. The checklist of vascular plant species and subspecies in the Velika plaža and its vicinity in Ulcinj.

Divisio PTERIDOPHYTA

Classis LYCOPSIDA

Familia SELAGINELLACEAE

Selaginella denticulata (L.) Spring* / semp Ch herb rept; evr-az; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Classis SPHENOPSIDA

Familia EQUISETACEAE

Equisetum palustre L. / v-a Mes-Mac G rhiz; evr-sam (cirkumhol)

Equisetum ramosissimum Desf. / A Meg-Alt G rhiz; evr-az

Equisetum telmateia Ehrh. / a Meg-Alt G rhiz; sr.evr-med-atl-sj.am (bor-merid)

Classis FILICOPSIDA

Familia OPHIOGLOSSACEAE

Ophioglossum azoricum C. Presl. / a N-Mes G rhiz; cirkhol; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia ADIANTACEAE

Adiantum capillus-veneris L.* / a Mi-Mes G rhiz caesp; cirkhol; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Familia HYPOLEPIDACEAE

Pteridium aquilinum (L.) Kuhn. in Kersten / a Meg-Alt G rhiz; kosm; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia ASPLENIACEAE

Asplenium adiantum-nigrum L.* / Mes semp Ch herb caesp; kosm; (Rohlena 1904; 1942)

Asplenium ceterach L.* / poik Mi Ch herb caesp-semiros; evr-z. az; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)

Asplenium onopteris L.* / Mes semp Ch herb caesp; cirk-med; (Lakušić et al. 2006)

Asplenium ruta-muraria L.* / Mi semp Ch herb caesp; evr-sam (cirkumhol); (Rohlena 1904)

Asplenium trichomanes L.* / a Meg-Alt G rhiz; kosm; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Familia WOODSIACEAE

Cystopteris fragilis (L.) Bernh in Schreder* / Mes-Meg Ch herb semiros; kosm; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Familia DRYOPTERIDACEAE

Dryopteris pallida (Bory) C. Chr ex Maire & Petitmengin* / Mes-Meg G rhiz; med-subm-or; (Rohlena 1942)

Dryopteris villarii (Bellarsi) Schins & Thell* / a Mes G rhiz; (temp) submerid-merid-mont-subalp (alp); (Rohlena 1904, 1911)

Divisio SPERMATOPHYTA

Phyllum GYMNOSPERMAE

Classis CONIFEROPSIDA

Familia PINACEAE

Pinus halepensis Miller / ac semp Mes P scap; med; NATURA 2000-2270*

Pinus nigra Arnold / ac semp Mes P scap; c.e.JEP; NATURA 2000-2270*

Pinus pinaster Aiton / ac semp Mes P scap; med-atl; NATURA 2000-2270*

Pinus pinea L. / ac semp Mes P scap; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2270*

Familia CUPRESSACEAE

Cupressus sempervirens L. / ac semp Mes P scap; i.med-submed-or

Juniperus oxycedrus L.* / ac semp Mi-Mes P caesp/P scap; med-submed-or; (Rohlena 1904, 1942; Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Juniperus horizontalis Moench.* / ac semp Mi P caesp/P scap; ADV (sj. am); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Juniperus virginiana L.* / ac semp Mi-Mes P caesp/P scap; med-submed-or; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Thuja orientalis L. / ac semp Mes P scap; cirk-med

Classis GNETOPSIDA

Familia EPHEDRACEAE

Ephedra campylopoda C. A. Mayer* / fo semp S lig; i.med; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942; Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Ephedra distachya L. / fo dec NP caesp; aralocasp-j.sib-pont-(pann)+(calp)-j.atl; NATURA 2000-2270*

Phyllum ANGIOSPERMAE

Classis DICOTYLEDONES

Familia SALICACEAE

Populus alba L. / v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap; sr.evr-med-submed-pont-j.sib-tur; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Populus canescens (Aiton) Sm.* / v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap; evr-sam; (Stešević and Drescher 2011)

Populus deltoides Marshall / v fo dec Mes P scap; evr-sam; NATURA 2000-92A0

Populus nigra L. / v fo dec Mes P scap; sr.evr-med-pont-j.s.sib; NATURA 2000-92A0

Populus tremula L. / v fo dec Mes P scap; evr-az-(bor-merid); NATURA 2000-92A0

Salix alba L. / n-v fo dec Mes P scap; evr; NATURA 2000-92A0

Salix elaeagnos Scop.* v fo dec Mi P scap; S(J)EP; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Salix purpurea L. v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap, sr.evr-sr.j.sib-med-z.or; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia BETULACEAE

Alnus glutinosa (L.) Gaertner / v fo dec Mes P scap; sr.evr; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia CORYLACEAE

Carpinus betulus L.* / v fo dec Mes P scap; evr-med-z.az; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Carpinus orientalis Miller / v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap/P caesp; c.i.med-submed-z.or; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Corylus avellana L.* / v fo dec Mi P caesp; boreoatl-sr.evr-med-submed-j.z.az

Ostrya carpinifolia Scop. / v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap, c.i.med-c.i.submed; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia FAGACEAE

Castanea sativa Miller.* / v fo dec Mes P scap; z.med-z.c.submed-eux-hyrc; (Rohlena 1904; Aalto et al. 1972; Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Quercus cerris L.* / v fo dec Mi - Mes P scap; c.i.submed-illyr-balk-pan; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Quercus coccifera L. /Donji Štoj; med; NATURA 2000-2270*

Quercus frainetto Ten. / v fo semp Mi P caesp; c.med-c.submed-balc-danub-pann; NATURA 2000-92A0

Quercus ilex L.* / v fo semp Mi-Mes P scap/P caesp; med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942; Adamović L. 1911; Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Quercus pubescens Willd.* / v fo dec Mes P scap; c.i.med-submed-pan.danub-j.subatl; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Quercus robur L. ssp. *scutariensis* Černjavski / v fo dec Mes P scap; med-submed (illyr); *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Quercus trojana Webb in London* / v fo dec Mes P scap; med-c.subm (j.apen-j.i.illir-balk-anatol); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Familia ULMACEAE

Celtis australis L. / v fo dec Mes P scap; med-c.submed

Ulmus canescens Melville / v fo dec Mes P scap; c.i.med; NATURA 2000-92A0

Ulmus minor Miller. / n fo dec Mi - Mes P scap; med-arm-pont-j.atl-j.sarm; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia MORACEAE

Broussonetia papyrifera (L.) Vent / n-v fo dec Mi-Mes P caesp; ADV (i.az)

Ficus carica L. / n-v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap; med-submed-or-j.atl; NATURA 2000-92A0

Morus alba L. / v fo dec Mes P scap;ADV (az); NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia CANNABACEAE

Canabis sativa L.* / a Mes T scap; ADV (az); (Adamović L.1913)

Humulus lupulus L. / v-a Alt SH herb;kosm

Familia URTICACEAE

- Parietaria judaica* L. / n-aut Mi-Mac H scap; atl-med-submed-or
Parietaria vulgaris Hill. / n-aut Mi-Mac H scap; atl-med-submed-or
Urtica dioica L. / v-aut Mes-Alt H scap; cirkhol (bor-temp)
Urtica pilulifera L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed
Urtica urens L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; cirkhol (bor-temp); NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia SANTALACEAE

- Osyris alba* L.* / fo semp NP caesp, z.i.med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942; Adamović L. 1913)
Thesium arvense Horvatovszky* / a Mes H scap; i.med-or-turcest-j.sib-pont-pann; (Rohlena 1902b)
Thesium divaricatum Jan ex Mert & Koch in Rohling* / a Mes-Meg H scap; med-submed-or; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)

Familia ARISTOLOCHIACEAE

- Aristolochia clematitis* L. / v-a Mes-Meg G rad scap; submed-pont; NATURA 2000-92A0
Aristolochia rotunda L. / v-a Mes G tub; med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia POLYGONACEAE

- Fallopia convolvulus* (L.) A. Love* / v-a Mes-Meg ST herb; submed-z.him(atl)-sarm-pont-sr.sib; (Adamović L. 1913)
Polygonum aviculare L. / a-aut Mi-Meg T rept; kosm
Polygonum bellardi All. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-92A0
Polygonum lapathifolium L. / a-aut Mac-Alt T scap; kosm (evr-sam); NATURA 2000-2190
Polygonum maritimum L. / a Mes-Mac H rept; kosm; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*;
Sporobolo-elymentum farcti; NATURA 2000-2110, 2220
Polygonum persicaria L. / a-aut Mes-Mac T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-92A0
Polygonum salicifolium Brouss. ex Willd / a Mes-Mac H scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-92A0
Rumex acetosella L. / a Mes-Meg H scap; kosm (evr-sam)
Rumex acetosella L. ssp. *multifidus** / a Mes-Meg H scap; kosm (evr-sam); (Rohlena 1942; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Rumex conglomeratus Murray / a Meg H scap; z.sarm-atl-med-turcest-pann; NATURA 2000-6420, 2190
Rumex crispus L. / a Mes-Meg H scap; kosm (evr); NATURA 2000-6420, 2190
Rumex hydrolapathum Hudson / a Mes-Meg H scap; se-med-subm-z.pont; NATURA 2000-6420, 2190
Rumex obtusifolius L.* / a Mes-Meg H scap; sr.evr-med-hirc-sr.pont; (Rohlena 1904)
Rumex palustris Sm. / a Mes-Meg T scap; kosm (evr); NATURA 2000-2190
Rumex pulcher L. / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; med(or)-submed-pann-(j.atl); NATURA 2000-2190

Familia CHENOPODIACEAE

- Atriplex litoralis* L.* / a-aut Mes-Alt T scap;turan-subsib-pann+med disj.-me-circbott-lit; (Adamović L. 1913)
Atriplex oblongifolia Waldst & Kit / a Mes-Meg T scap; evr-pont
Atriplex patula L.* / aut Meg-Alt T scap; ADV (sj.am); (Adamović L. 1913)
Atriplex prostrata Boucher ex DC. in Lam & DC. / a-aut Mes-Alt T scap/T rept; cirkhol; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*;
Agropyretum mediterraneum; NATURA 2000-2110
Beta vulgaris L. ssp. *maritima* (L.) / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; se-evr-pont; NATURA 2000-1310
Camphorosma monspeliaca L.* / a Mac Ch frut caesp; sr.evr-j.s.sib; (Adamović L. 1913)
Chenopodium album L. / a-aut Meg-AltT scap; kosm
Chenopodium ambrosioides L. / a-aut Mes-AltT scap; kosm
Chenopodium botrys L. / a-aut Mes-MacT scap; evr-az
Chenopodium hybridum L. / a Mes-Meg T scap; evr-sam
Chenopodium multifidum L. / a-aut Mes-MacH scap; ADV (j.am)
Chenopodium murale L. / a-aut Mac-MegT scap; kosm (med)
Chenopodium polyspermum L. / a-aut Mes-MacT scap; sr.evr-j.s.sib-submed-pont;
Chenopodium strictum J. Mur / a Mes T scap; kosm
Chenopodium vulvaria L. / a-aut Mes- Meg T scap; evr-med-pont-tur-c.az
Halimione portulacoides (L.) Aellen / a Mes-Mac Ch frut rept/NP rept; med-atl; NATURA 2000-1310
Polycnemum majus A. Braun* / a Mi-Mes T scap; (turcest)z.pont-pann-submed-herc-polon; (Adamović L. 1913)
Salicornia europaea L. / aut Mes-Mac T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-1310
Salicornia fruticosa (L.) L. / aut Mes Ch herb succ; j.evr-med; NATURA 2000-1310
Salsola kali L. / v-a Mes-MacT scap; evr-az; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; NATURA 2000-2110

Salsola soda L. / a Mes-Alt T scap; j.evr-pont; NATURA 2000-2110
Spinacia oleracea L. / a Mes T scap; ADV (j.z.az)
Suaeda maritima (L.) Dumort / a-aut Mes-Alt T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-1310
Suaeda maritima (L.) Dumort ssp. *salsa* (L.) Soo in Soo & Jav / a-aut Mes-Alt T scap; kosm
Suaeda vera J. F. Gmelin in L. / a-aut fo dec NP caesp; kosm

Familia AMARANTHACEAE

Amaranthus albus L. / a-aut Mes-Alt T scap; ADV (sj. am)
Amaranthus cruentus L. / a-aut Mac T scap; ADV (sj. am)
Amaranthus hybridus L. / a Mes-Mac T scap; ADV (sj. am)

Familia NYCTAGINACEAE

Bougainvillea glabra Choisy / fo semp S lig; ADV (j. am)
Mirabilis jalapa L. / v-a Mes G bulb; ADV (j. am)

Familia PHYTOLACCACEAE

Phytolacca americana L. / a-aut Alt G rhiz; ADV (sj. am)

Familia AIZOACEAE

Carpobrotus edulis (L.) N. E. Br. In E. P. Phillips / v-a Alt Ch suffr; ADV (j. afr.)
Lampranthus deltooides (L.) Glen ex Wijnands / v-a Alt Ch suffr; ADV (j. afr.)

Familia PORTULACACEAE

Portulaca oleracea L. / a-aut Mes T scap; ADV (az)

Familia CARYOPHYLLACEAE

Arenaria spryillifolia L. / v-a Mi T scap; kosm
Cerastium brachypetalum Pers. / v N-Mi T scap semiros; egej-submed-pann-j. atl-(c.evr)
Cerastium glomeratum Thuill. / v-a N-Mi T scap semiros; kosm; NATURA 2000-92A0
Cerastium ligusticum Viv. ssp. *ligusticum** / v Mes-Mac T scap semiros; JEP (illyr- apen); (Rohlena 1904)
Cerastium pumilum Curtis ssp. *glutinatum* (Fries) Jalas / v Mi-Mes T scap; evr-med-z.az
Dianthus armeria L. / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap/H scap bienn; submed-z.pont-j. atl-j. z. sarm; NATURA 2000-92A0
Gypsophila muralis L. / a Mes T scap; evr-az
Herniaria glabra L. / a N Ch herb-rept/T rept; evr-az
Lychnis flos-cuculi L. / v-a Mes-Mac H scap; se-ev(bor)-subm-pont-j.sib
Minuartia hybrida (Vill) Schischkin in Komarov* / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed-or; (Rohlena 1902a)
Minuartia mediterranea (Ledeb) K. Maly / v Mi-Mes T scap; atl-med-illyr
Minuartia viscosa (Schreber) Schinz & Thell / v Mi T scap; c. evr-i. submed-pont-j. sib-i. med; (Rohlena 1942)
Moenchia mantica (L.) Bartl / v Mi-Mes T scap; i.med-ci.submed
Petrorhagia obcordata (Margot & Reuter) Greuter & Burdet* / v-a Mes T scap; med-submed (illyr-balk); (Adamović L. 1913)
Petrorhagia prolifera (L.) P. W. Ball & Heywood / v-a Mes T scap; z. med-z. c. submed-pann-j. atl
Petrorhagia saxifraga (L.) Link / v-a Mes Ch herb caesp; (c. med)-submed-z. pann-z. pont
Polycarpon tetraphyllum (L.) L. / v-a Mi T scap; med-submed-j. atl
Polycarpon tetraphyllum (L.) L. ssp. *alsinifolium* (Biv.) Ball. / v-a Mi T scap; med-submed-j. atl
Sagina apetala Ard. / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-or-submed-atl-j. c. evr
Saponaria officinalis L. / a-aut Mes-Meg H scap; sr. evr-(sr.sib)-submed-z.pont
Scleranthus annuus L. / v-aut Mi T scap/H bienn; med
Silene bellidifolia Juss. ex Jacq / v-a Mes T scap; j.med; NATURA 2000-2240
Silene conica L. / a Mi-Mes T scap; z.i.med-submed-pont-or-tur; NATURA 2000-2240
Silene cretica L. / a Mi-Mes T scap; i. med
Silene gallica L. / v Mes T scap; kosm
Silene gallinyi Reichenb / a Mes T scap; i. med-submed (illyr-apen)
Silene italica (L.) Pers / v-a Mes-Mac H scap semiros; med-submed-arm (pann)
Silene latifolia Poiret ssp. *latifolia* / v-a Mes-Meg T scap/H scap bienn; evr-az (bor-merid); NATURA 2000-92A0
Silene nocturna L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; cirk-med
Silene vulgaris (Moench) Garcke ssp. *angustifolia* Hayek / v-aut Mac-Meg H scap/G rad; evr-az (bor-merid)
Stellaria media (L.) Vill / n-aut Mi-Meg T rept; kosm; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Familia NYMPHAEACEAE

Nymphaea alba L. / a rhiz nat Hyd G; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia RANUNCULACEAE

Adonis annua L.* / v Mes-Mac T scap; v Mes-Mac T scap; (Baldacci 1900; Rohlena 1942)

Anemone apenina L. / n-v Mi-Mes G rhiz; i. med-submed; (Rohlena 1904)

Anemone hortensis L. / n-v Mes G rhiz; c. i. med-c. submed

Clematis flamula L. / v-a fo dec Alt S lig; med-(c.submed); NATURA 2000-2240, 92A0

Clematis vitalba L.* / v-a fo dec Alt S lig; evr; (Janković end Bogojević 1965)

Clematis viticella L. / v-aut fo dec Alt S lig; c. i. med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0

Consolida ajacis (L.) Schur / a Mes-Mac T scap; z. c. submed; NATURA 2000-2270*

Delphinium peregrinum L.* / a Mes-Mac T scap; sr. evr; (Adamović R. Ž. 1968)

Nigella arvensis L. / a-aut Mes T scap; j.c.evr-j.subatl-med-or-z. pont

Ranunculus ficaria L. / v Mi G tub; sr.evr; NATURA 2000-92A0

Ranunculus flammula L. / a-aut Mi-Meg rad emer Hyd G; cirkhol (subarct-temp); NATURA 2000-2190

Ranunculus marginatus D'Urv / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; i. med-subm; NATURA 2000-2190

Ranunculus millefoliatus Vahl. / v-a Mes G tub; c. i. med-subm

Ranunculus muricatus L. / v Mi-Mes T scap semiros; med-or-(turan)-submed; NATURA 2000-2190

Ranunculus sardous Crantz. / v-a Mes-Mac T semiros; c. evr-med-or-pann-subatl

Ranunculus trichophyllus Chaix in Vill. / v-a rad nat-sbm Hyd T/G; se; NATURA 2000-2190

Ranunculus velutinus Ten. / a Meg H scap; med-submed

Thalictrum aquilegifolium L. / v-a Meg-Alt H scap; z. c. submed-c. evr-sarm; NATURA 2000-92A0

Thalictrum lucidum L.* / a Meg-Alt H scap; c. (i. submed)-z. pont-pann-c. evr-sarm; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Familia BERBERIDACEAE

Mahonia aquifolium (Pursh) Nutt / v fo semp NP caesp; ADV (sj. am)

Familia MAGNOLIACEAE

Magnolia grandiflora L. / a fo semp NP scap; ADV (sj. am)

Familia LAURACEAE

Laurus nobilis L. / v fo semp Mi P scap/P caesp; i. med-jadr-eux

Familia PAPAVERACEAE

Chelidonium majus L. / v-aut Mes-Mac H semiros; atl-sr. evr-med-z. az (bor-merid); NATURA 2000-92A0

Fumaria capreolata L.* / v Mes ST herb; z. c. med-atl;

Fumaria flaabellata Gaspar* / v Mes ST herb; i. med; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Fumaria officinalis L. / a M-Mes T scap; kosm

Glaucium flavum Crantz. / a-aut Mes-Meg H scap; med-(or)-atl

Papaver rhoeas L. / v-a Mac-Meg T scap; atl-j. z. sarm-med-or-(pont)

Familia BRASSICACEAE

Alliaria petiolata (Bieb) C.&G. / v Meg H scap bienn; sr. evr-med-tur-pont; NATURA 2000-92A0

Alyssum minus (L.) Rothm / v N-Mi T scap; med-submed pont

Alyssoides utriculata (L.) Medicus* / v Mes-Meg Ch suffr caesp; JEP (z. i. submed-z. alp-karp) (Baldacci 1891; Rohlena 1942)

Arabidopsis thaliana (L.) Heynh in Holl & Heynh*/ v Mi-Mes T scap semiros; evr-az (bor-merid)

Arabis hirsuta L. / v-a Mes-Meg H semiros bienn; cirkhol (bor-merid); NATURA 2000-92A0

Arabis turrata L.* / v Meg H scap bienn, med-submed-pann-(z. pont)-j. subatl; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Arabis verna (L.) R. Br. in Aiton* / n-v N-Mac T semiros; med-submed; (Rohlena 1904,1942)

Berberoa mutabilis (Vent) DC. / a-aut Mes-Mac H scap; med-submed (illyr-mac-z. egej-apan); NATURA 2000-92A0

Berberoa obliqua (Sm.) DC. / a-aut Mes-Mac H scap; j. app-hel-thrac

Brassica fruticulosa Cyr.* / n-aut Mes-Mac H semiros/Ch suffr; stenomed; (Rohlena 1942)

Brassica nigra (L.) Koch in Rohling / v-a Meg-Alt T semiros; kosm

Bunias erucago L. / v-a Mes-Meg T semiros/H scap bienn; med-submed

Cakile maritima Scop. / v-a Mi-Meg T scap-rept; med-atl; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*, NATURA 2000-2110

Calepina irregularis (Asso) Thell in Schinz & R. Keller / n-v Mes-Meg T scap semiros; med-or-(tur)-pont-(pann-j. subatl)

- Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) **Medicus** / n-ut Mi-Meg T scap semiros/H semiros bienn; kosm (submed)
Capsella rubella **Reuter** / n-v Mi T semiros; med-z.c.submed-j.subatl
Cardamine amara L.* / v-a Mi-Mes H scap; evr-az; (Rohlena 1904)
Cardamine graeca L.* / v Mi-Mes T semiros; med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Cardamine hirsuta L. / v Mi-Mes T semiros; evr-az (bor-merid); NATURA 2000-92A0
Cardamine pratensis L. / a Mes-Mac H scap; evr-sam; NATURA 2000-92A0
Cardaria draba (L.) **Desv.** / a Mes-Mac G rhiz/H scap; med-or-tur; (Adamović 1913)
Clypeola jonthlaspi L. / a Mi T scap; med
Coronopus squamatus (**Forskal**) **Ascherson** / v-a Mi T rept; c. evr-atl-med-z.pont-pann; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Diplotaxis muralis (L.) **DC.** / v Mes T semiros; c. evr-atl-(med)-submed-pann
Diplotaxis tenuifolia (L.) **DC.** / a Mes H semiros; c. evr-atl-c. med-c. (i.) submed-pann
Draba muralis L.* / v Mi-Mes T scap semiros; med-submed-atl-c. evr (Rohlena 1904, 1942; Adamović L. 1913)
Erophila verna (L.) **Chevoll ssp. verna** / v N-Mi T ros; sr. evr-med-or-turan-pont
Eruca vesicaria (L.) **Cav** / a Mes-Mac T scap semiros; eurimed-turan
Erysimum cheiri (L.) **Crantz*** / v-a Mac-Meg H scap; ADV (evr); (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Hornungia petraea (L.) **Reichenb*** / a Mi-Mes T scap semiros; z. (i) med-submed-atl-j. subatl; (Rohlena 1902a, 1904, 1942)
Iberis umbellata L.* / v-a Mac T scap; c. submed (illyr-apan); (Adamović L. 1913)
Lepidium campestre (L.) **R. Br. In Aiton** / v-a Mac T scap semiros; sr. evr-submed-pont-pann
Lepidium graminifolium L.* / v-a MesH scap; v-a MesH scap; (Adamović L. 1913)
Lobularia maritima (L.) **Desv.** / v-aut Mi-Mes H scap/Ch suffr; stenomed
Matthiola sinuata (L.) **R. Br. in Aiton** / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; med-atl
Nasturtium officinale **R.Br. in Aiton*** / a Mi rhiz emer Hyd G; evr-az (bor-temp); NATURA 2000-92A0
Peltaria alliacea **Jacq.*** / v-a Mac H scap; illyr-j. karp-pann; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Raphanus raphanistrum L. / v-a Meg T scap; kosm (med-submed)
Rapistrum rugosum (L.) **All.*** / v-a Mes-Mac T semiros; eurimed; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)
Sisymbrium officinale (L.) **Scop** / v-a Mac-Meg T scap semiros; evr-az (bor-merid); NATURA 2000-92A0
Sisymbrium polyceratium L.* / v-a Mac-Meg T scap semiros; eurimed; (Rohlena 1902a; 1942)
Thlaspi perfoliatum L. / v Mi-Mes T scap semiros; med-tur-pont-pann-herc-j. atl+z. balt

Familia RESEDACEAE

- Reseda inodora* **Reichenb** / a Mes-Meg H scap; med-submed-pont;
Reseda lutea L.* / a Mes-Meg H scap; sr. evr-med-submed; (Baldacci 1900; Rohlena 1942)
Reseda phyteuma L. / v-aut Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed-pann-j. subatl

Familia CRASSULACEAE

- Sedum hispanicum* L.* / v-a Mi Ch herb succ; i. med-submed-pont; (Rohlena 1931, 1942)
Sedum litoreum **Guss.*** / v Mes-Meg T succ; med-or; (Rohlena 1903, 1942)
Umbilicus rupestris (**Salisb**) **Dandy in Riddelsd*** / v Mi-Mes G bulb; med-atl; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)

Familia HYDRANGEACEAE

- Philadelphus coronarius* L.* / fo dec Mi P caesp/P scap; ADV (evr); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Familia PITTOSPORACEAE

- Pittosporum tobira* (**Thunb**) **Aiton** / v semp NP suffr; ADV (i.az)

Familia PLATANACEAE

- Platanus acerifolia* (**Aiton**) **Willd** / v-a Mes Pscap; evr-med

Familia SAXIFRAGACEAE

- Saxifraga tridactylites* L.* / n-v Mi T semiros; c. evr-pann-atl-med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Familia CAESALPINACEAE

- Poinciana gilliesii* **Hook.** / a fo dec N Mi P caesp; ADV (j. am)

Familia ROSACEAE

- Agrimonia eupatoria* L. / a-aut Mac-Meg H scap; sr. evr-med-pont-j.sib-or-tur; NATURA 2000-92A0
Aphanes arvensis L.* / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; evr; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Crataegus monogyna **Jacq.** / v fo dec NP caesp; sr.evr-med-subm-pont; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Cydonia oblonga Miller. / v-aut fo dec Mi P scap; ADV (j. z. az.)
Fragaria vesca L.* / v-a Mes H semiros rept; cirkhol (boreo-submerid); (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Geum urbanum L. / v-a Mac H scap semiros; evr-z.az-s.am-(bor-temp); NATURA 2000-92A0
Malus domestica Borkh / v fo dec Mi P scap; ADV (c. az.)
Potentilla fruticosa L.* / fo dec Mi P caesp/P scap; cirkumbor; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)
Potentilla hirta L.* / a Mi-Mes H scap; j.evr-med; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)
Potentilla reptans L. / a Mi-Mes H rept; kosm (evr); NATURA 2000-92A0
Prunus cerasifera Ehrh. / v fo dec Mi P caesp/P scap; az-pont
Prunus laurocerasus L.* / v fo dec Mi P caesp/P scap; ADV (sj. am); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)
Prunus spinosa L. / v fo dec Mi NP caesp; j.atl-sarm-(z.med)-submed-pont-pann; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*;
 NATURA 2000-92A0
Rosa sempervirens L. / v-a fo semp NP caesp; z. (i) med-provans-cirkjadr-(j. atl); NATURA 2000-92A0
Rubus ulmifolius Schott. / v-a fo dec NP rept; makar-z.med-z.c.submed-armor; NATURA 2000-92A0
Sanguisorba minor Scop ssp. *muricata* Briq. / a Mes-Meg H semiros; med-submed-(or)-tur; NATURA 2000-2130*
Spiraea x fontenaysii (Lebas.) Zabel* / fo dec NP caesp, ADV (i. az); (Bunuševac 1977)
Spiraea japonica L.* / fo dec NP caesp, ADV (i. az); (Bunuševac 1977)
Spiraea x vanhouttei (Briot) Zabel* fo semp S lig; ADV (am); (Bunuševac 1977)

Familia FABACEAE

Amorpha fruticosa L. / fo dec NP caesp; ADV (sj.am)
Anthyllis vulneraria L. ssp. *praepropera* (A. Kernner) Bornm* / v-a Mec-Meg H scap; med-submed; (Rohlena 1942)
Anthyllis vulneraria L. ssp. *weldeniana* (Reichenb) Culler* / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; med-submed; (Rohlena 1902a)
Astragalus glycyphyllos L.* / v-a Mac-Meg H rept; evr-i. submed-pont-j.sib-tur; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Astragalus hamosus L.* / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-tur; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)
Chamaecytisus hirsutus (L.) Link* / v-a fo dec Mes-Meg Ch suffr caesp; c.i.med-submed; (Rohlena 1942)
Colutea arborescens L.* / v-a fo dec Mi P caesp; z.med-z.c.submed-(j.subatl)-pan; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)
Coronilla emerus L. ssp. *emeroides* (Boiss & Spruner) Hayek / a Meg-Alt Ch frut; i.med-i.submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Coronilla scorpioides L.* / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-or-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Coronilla valentina L.* / v fo dec NP caesp; c.med; (Rohlena 1942)
Dorycnium hirsutum (L.) Ser in DC. / v-a Mes Ch suffr caesp; med-z.c.submed; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0
Dorycnium pentaphyllum Scop. ssp. *herbaceum* (Vill.) Rouy. / v-a Mes Ch suffr caesp; c.med-c.i.submed-pann-pont;
 NATURA 2000-2190
Galega officinalis L. / v-a Meg H scap; c.i.submed-pann-pont-(j.c.evr)
Genista tinctoria L. / v-a fo dec Meg Ch suffr caesp; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-2130*
Hippocrepis ciliata Willd. / v Mi-Mes T scap; med
Hippocrepis unisiliquosa L.* / v Mes T scap; med-c. submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Hymenocarpus circinatus (L.) Savi* v Mi-Mes H scap; stenomedit; (Adamović L. 1913)
Lathyrus aphaca L. / v-a Mes T scap; med-turkest-submed-pann-j.atl-j.subatl
Lathyrus cicera L. / v-a Mes T scap; med-or-submed
Lathyrus sphaericus Retz. / v-a Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed-(j.subatl+j.z.atl); NATURA 2000-2190
Lathyrus venetus (Mill) Wohlf* / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; c.i.submed-j. karp-(z.pont); (Rohlena 1904)
Lens ervoides (Briq) Grande* / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Lotus angustissimus L. / a Mes-Mac T scap; euri.med-pont-pann; NATURA 2000-2190
Lotus corniculatus L. / v-aut Mes H scap; evr-z.az-(bor-mer)-i.af-(subtro-tro); NATURA 2000-2190
Lotus ornithopodioides L.* / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; (Rohlena 1942)
Lotus parviflorus Desv.* / v-a Mes T scap; stenomed; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Lotus tenuis Waldst. & Kit. E Willd / a Mes H scap; evr-af; NATURA 2000-2190
Lupinus angustifolius L.* / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; (Adamović L. 1913)
Medicago arabica (L.) Hudson / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed-or-tur
Medicago litoralis Rohde ex Loisel / v Mi-Mes T scap; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120
Medicago lupulina L. / a-aut Mi-Mes T scap/H scap; evr-i. afr
Medicago marina L. / v- a Mes Ch rept; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110
Medicago minima (L.) L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-2130*
Medicago orbicularis (L.) Bartol / v Mes-Mac T rept; med-submed-or-tur

- Medicago polymorpha* L. / v Mes T rept; makar-med-or-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Medicago prostrata Jacq.* / a Mes H rept; c. submed-pann; (Rohlena 1942)
Medicago rigidula (L.) All. / v Mes-Mac T rept; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Medicago scutellata L. (Miller) / v Mes-Mac T scap; evr-med; (Baldacci 1910; Rohlena 1942)
Melilotus alba Medicus* / a-aut Mac-Alt T scap; evr-az;(Adamović L. 1913; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Melilotus indica (L.) All* / v Mes-Meg T scap; medit-turm; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)
Onobrychis caput-gali (L.) Lam / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2110, 2130*
Ononis pusilla L. / a Mes Ch semi-caesp; a Mes Ch semi-caesp
Ononis reclinata L.* / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; abes-med-submed-j. atl; (Rohlena 1902a, 1933, 1942)
Ononis spinosa L.* / a Mes Ch semi-caesp; evr-med; (Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Ononis viscosa L. ssp. *breviflora* (DC.) Nyman* / a Mes T scap; med; (Rohlena 1902a,1942)
Ornithopus compressus L.* / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; eurimed; (Adamović L. 1913)
Petteria ramentacea (Sieber) C. Presl* / v fo dec NP caesp; c.i.med-submed-(illyr-balk); (Rohlena 1904, 1942; Bunuševac et al. 1977)
Pisum sativum L. ssp. *elatius* (Bieb) Ascherson & Graebner / v Mi-Mes H scap; stenomed
Psoralea bituminosa L. / a Mes H scap; eurimed
Robinia pseudoacacia L. / fo dec Mi-Mes P caesp/P scap; ADV (sj.am); NATURA2000-2270*
Scorpiurus muricatus L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2190
Securigera securidaca (L.) Degen & Dorfler / v-a Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Spartium junceum L. / v fo dec NP caesp; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2270*
Trifolium angustifolium L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Trifolium arvense L.* / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; evr-med-pont-j. sib; (Baldacci 1900; Rohlena 1942; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Trifolium campestre Schreber in Sturm / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; abes+med-or-z.pont-atl-j.z.sarm; NATURA 2000-2130*, 92A0
Trifolium cherleri L.* / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed;(Rohlena 1942)
Trifolium cinctum DC.* / v Mi-Mes T scap; evr-med; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)
Trifolium lappaceum L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Trifolium medium L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; evr; NATURA 2000-92A0
Trifolium nigrescens Div. / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Trifolium ochroleucum Hudson / v-a Mes-Mac H scap; sr. evr-submed-pont; NATURA 2000-92A0
Trifolium physodes Steven ex Bieb / v-a Mes H scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Trifolium pratense L. / a Mes H scap; evr
Trifolium repens L. / v-a Mi-Mes H rept; cirkhol (ark-submer); NATURA 2000-92A0
Trifolium resupinatum L. / a Mes T rept/H rept; makar-med-or-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Trifolium scabrum L. / v-a Mi-Mes T rept; med- z. c. submed-atl-j. subatl; NATURA 2000-2130*
Trifolium stelatum L. / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240
Trifolium subteraneum L. / v Mi-Mes H rept; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240
Trifolium tenuifolium Ten.* / a Mes-Mac T scap; eurimed; (Baldacci 1900)
Trifolium tomentosum L. / v-a Mi-Mes T rept; med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0, 2240
Trigonella corniculata (L.) L. / v Mes-Mac T scap; stenomed
Trigonella monspeliaca L.* / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed-pann-(j. atl); (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)
Vicia bithynica (L.) L. / v Mes-Mac H scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240
Vicia grandiflora Scop.* / v-a Mes-Meg H scap/T scap; c.i.subm-or-z.pont-pann (Rohlena 1904)
Vicia hybrida L. / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Vicia melanops Sibth. & Sm. / a Mes-Meg T scap/ST herb; i.med; NATURA 2000-92A0
Vicia tenuifolia Roth. / v-a Mes H scap; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-2240, 92A0
Vicia villosa Roth. / v-a Mac-Alt ST herb/H bienn; med-submed-(atl-subatl); NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia OXALIDACEAE

- Oxalis articulata* Savigniy in Lam. / a Mes G rhiz; ADV (j. am.)
Oxalis corniculata L. / v-a Mi-Mes H rept; kosm (submed)

Familia GERANIACEAE

- Erodium botrys* (Cav.) Bertol* / v Mi-Mac T scap; med-submed; (Baldacci 1910; Rohlena 1942)
Erodium cicutarium (L.) L'Her. in Aiton / v-a Mi-Mes T scap semiros; kosm; NATURA 2000-92A0
Erodium malacoides (L.)L'Her. / n-v Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed

Erodium moschatum (L.)L'Her. / v Mes-Meg T scap/H bienn; evr; NATURA 2000-92A0
Geranium brutium Gaspar.* / n-v Mes-Mac T semiros; s. i.med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Geranium columbinum L. / v-a Mes T scap semiros; med-submed-pann-atl-c.evr; NATURA 2000-92A0
Geranium dissectum L. / v-a Mes T semiros; med-or-submed-pann-atl-c.evr
Geranium lucidum L.* / v-a Mi-Meg T scap semiros; evr; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Geranium molle L. / n-v Mi-Mes T semiros; evr-afr; NATURA 2000-92A0
Geranium purpureum (Vill) Nyman / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Geranium robertianum L. / v-aut Mi-Mes T scap semiros; kosm; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0
Geranium rotundifolium L. / v-aut Mes-Mac T scap semiros; sr.evr-tur-pont-j.sib-med-submed

Familia ZYGOPHYLLOACEAE

Tribulus terrestris L. / a-aut Mi-Meg T rept; kosm (afr)

Familia LINACEAE

Linum bienne Miller / v-a Mes H scap bienn; med-submed-j.atl-brit-iber; NATURA 2000-2130*
Linum corymbulosum Reichenb / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Linum maritimum L. / a-aut Mi-Mes H scap; z.med
Linum nodiflorum L. / a Mes-Mac T scap;med-submed; (Adamović L. 1913)
Linum strictum L. / v Mes-Mac T scap; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2130*
Linum tenuifolium L. / v-a Mes Ch suffr caesp; c.i.submed-j. z.pont-pann-boh-j.subatl; NATURA 2000-2130 *
Linum trigynum L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; evr-afr; NATURA 2000-92A0
Linum usitatissimum L.* / a Mes-Mac T scap; ADV (sj. am.); (Rohlena 1904)
Radiola linoides Roth. / a-aut Mi T scap; paleotemp; NATURA 2000-1410, 2190

Familia EUPHORBIACEAE

Chrozophora tinctoria (L.) A. Juss. / a-aut Mes T scap; med-turan
Euphorbia amygdaloides L. / v-a Mac H scap; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-92A0
Euphorbia chamaesyce L. / a Mi T rept; med
Euphorbia characias L. ssp. *wulfenii* (Hoppe ex Koch) A. R. Sm. / v Meg-Alt Ch suffr; i.med-submed; NATURA 2000-2270*
Euphorbia cyparissias L. / a Mac-Meg H scap; c.evr; NATURA 2000-92A0
Euphorbia exigua L.* / a Mi-Mes T scap; z.(i.)med-z.c.submed-atl-j.ce; (Adamović L. 1913)
Euphorbia falcata L.* / a-aut Mi-Mes T scap; med-or-turcest-submed-(pont)-j.subatl; (Baldacci 1910; Rohlena 1942)
Euphorbia helioscopia L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; evr-az-(temp-merid)
Euphorbia hirsuta L. / a- aut Mes-Meg T scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-2190
Euphorbia maculata L. / v-aut Mi-Mes T rept; ADV (sj. am)
Euphorbia palustris L. / v-a rhiz emer Hyd G; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2190
Euphorbia paralias L. / a Mac Ch frut caesp; med-atl; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; *Sporobolo-elymentum farcti*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2110, 2120
Euphorbia pinea L.* / v-a Mes-Mac Ch suffr; z.c.med-z.c.submed; (Rohlena 1902b, 1904, 1942; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Euphorbia peplis L. / a-aut Mi-Mes T rept; med-atl; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110
Euphorbia peploides Gouan* / v-aut Mi T scap; eurosib; (Adamović L. 1913)
Euphorbia peplus L. / a-aut Mi-Mes T scap; kosm
Euphorbia platyphyllos L. / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap; submed pann-j.atl-j. brit-j.c.evr; NATURA 2000-2110
Euphorbia rigida Bieb.* / v-aut Mi-Mes Ch suffr; sr.evr-sudsib; (Baldacci 1910)
Euphorbia sequierana Nicker / a Mes-Meg G rad caesp; evr; NATURA 2000-92A0
Euphorbia spinosa L.* / v Mes Ch suffr caesp; med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Euphorbia teracina L. / v-a Mac-Meg T scap; med; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2220
Mercurialis annua L. / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed-atl-j.subatl-j.c.evr-(balt)

Familia RUTACEAE

Ruta chalepensis L.* / v-a Mes-Mac Ch suffr; med-submed; (Rohlena 1904)
Poncirus trifoliata Rat.* / a fo dec Mes P scap; ADV (i.az); (Caković et al. 2013)

Familia MELIACEAE

Melia azedarch L. / v-a fo dec Mes P scap; ADV (az.); NATURA 2000-2270*

Familia POLYGALACEAE

Polygala comosa Schkuhr.* / a Mi-Mes H scap; evr-az-(bor-temp); (Rohlena 1904)

Polygala nicaensis Risso ex Koch in Rohling ssp. *mediterranea* Chedat / v-a Mac-Meg H scap; alger-hytel-(balk) s.j.i.iber

Familia SIMAROBACEAE

Ailanthus altissima (Miller) Swingle / v-a fo dec Mes P scap; ADV (i. az.); NATURA 2000-2270*

Familia ANACARDIACEAE

Cotinus coggygria Scop. / v fo dec Mi P caesp; (i.med)-c.i.submed-pann-j.z.pont; NATURA 2000-2270 *, 92A0

Pistacia lentiscus L. / v fo semp N-Mi P caesp/P scap; canar-med-catal-provenc-c.submed-z.c.anat; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-2130*, 92A0

Pistacia terebinthus L.* / v fo dec Mi-Mes P caesp/P scap; canar-med-z.submed-mak; (Rohlena 1911, 1942; Martinić et al. 2006)

Rhus coriaria L. / v fo dec N-Mi P caesp; canar-med-submed-s.j.iran-z.pont; NATURA 2000-2270*

Familia ACERACEAE

Acer campestre L. / v fo dec Mes P scap; sr.evr-submed-pont; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia CELASTRACEAE

Euonymus europaeus L. / v fo dec N-Mi P caesp; c.med-s.j.i.iber-i.submed-z.sr.pont-j.z.sarm-atl; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia RHAMNACEAE

Paliurus spina-christi Miller / v fo dec Mi P scap; med-submed-z.pont; NATURA 2000-92A0

Rhamnus intermedius Stendel & Hochst* / v fo dec N-Mi P caesp; med-submed-(illyr-jadr-end); (Rohlena 1942)

Ziziphus jujuba Miller. / aut fo dec Mi P caesp; ADV (az)

Familia VITACEAE

Parthenocissus quinquefolia (L.) Planchon in A. & C. DC / fo dec S lig; ADV (am)

Familia TILIACEAE

Tilia tomentosa Moench.* / v fo dec Mes P scap; SJEP (i.med-sj.z.anat-illyr-j.i.karp); (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Familia MALVACEAE

Abutilon theophrasti Medicus / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap ; ADV (i.az.)

Alcea rosea L. / a Alt H scap; ADV (az.)

Althaea hirsuta L.* / a Mes T scap; med-submed-pann-pont-or; (Adamović L. 1913)

Althaea officinalis L. / a Meg-Alt H scap; aralokasp-j.sib-pont-j.c.evr-j.atl; NATURA 2000-92A0

Hibiscus syriacus L. / a fo dec Mi P caesp; ADV (i.az)

Lavatera thuringiaca L. / a-aut Alt H scap; c.med-c.submed

Malva neglecta Wallr. / a-aut Mes-Mac T scap;sr.evr-med-or-tur-pont

Malva sylvestris L. / v-a Meg-Alt H scap bienn; evr-az-(bor-mer); NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia ELAEAGNACEAE

Elaeagnus angustifolia L. / a fo semp Mi P scap; ADV (c.az.)

Elaeagnus commutata Bernh* / a fo semp Mi P scap; ADV (sj.am.); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Familia GUTTIFERAE

Hypericum perforatum L. ssp. *veronense* (Schrk) Frohl / a-aut Mes Meg H scap; evr-az (bor-mer); NATURA 2000-2240, 2130*

Familia VIOLACEAE

Viola canina L. / v Mi-Mes H scap semiros; evr-az; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Viola odorata L. / v Mi-Mes H scap semiros; sr.evr-med-(mo)-s.iber-i.submed-s.z.pont

Familia CISTACEAE

Cistus incanus L. ssp. *creticus* (L.) Heywood. / v fo semp NP caesp; i. med; NATURA 2000-2130*

Cistus salvifolius L. / v fo semp NP caesp; med-z.c.submed-aquit; NATURA 2000-2130*

Fumana ericoides (Cav) Gaud in Maguier / v-a Mi-Mes Ch suffr rept; med-catal-j.gall-illyr; NATURA 2000-2130*

Fumana procumbens (Dunal) Gren & Godron / v-a Mi-Mes Ch suffr rept; (med-disj)-submed-hirc-matr-j.subatl-(herc+sj.z.balt); NATURA 2000-2270*

Fumana thymifolia (L) Spach ex Webl* / v-a Mi-Mes Ch suffr rept; med-submed; (Rohlena 1902a, 1911)

Helianthemum hirtum (L.) Miller* / v-a Mes-Meg Ch suffr; j.z.med; (Rohlena 1902a)

Helianthemum nummularium (L.) Miller ssp. *obscurum* (Čelak.) J. Holub / v-a Mes-Meg Ch suffr; v-a Mes-Meg Ch suffr; NATURA 2000-2270*, 2000-2130*

Helianthemum salicifolium (L.) Miller* / v Mes T scap; med-z.iran-submed-burgund; (Rohlena 1904; 1911)

Helianthemum tuberosum Gariault / v-a Mes-Meg Ch suffr; sr.evr-med-pont; NATURA 2000-2130*

Tuberaria guttata (L.) Fourr* / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed-j.atl; (Baldacci 1900; Adamović L. 1913)

Familia TAMARICACEAE

Tamarix africana Poiret / o dec N-Mi P caesp; z.med; NATURA 2000-2110, 1410, 2190, 92A0

Tamarix gallica L. / fo dec N-Mi P caesp; z.med; NATURA 2000-2110, 1410, 2190, 92A0

Familia CUCURBITACEAE

Citrullus lanatus (Thunb) Mausteld / a Mes ST herb; ADV (evr.az)

Cucurbita pepo L. / a Mes-Meg Trept; ADV (j.am.)

Ecballium elaterium (L.) Rich.* / v-a Mes-Meg G bulb; eurimed; (Adamović L. 1913)

Familia CACTACEAE

Opuntia ficus-indica (L.) Miller / a Mi-Meg P succ; ADV (j.am.)

Familia LYTHRACEAE

Lagerstroemia indica (L.) Pers.* / a Mi-Mes fo dec P caesp; ADV (i.az); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Lythrum hyssopifolia L. / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-1410, 2190

Lythrum salicaria L. / a Mac-Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190, 6420

Familia MYRTACEAE

Eucalyptus camaldulensis Dehnh* / v fo dec Mes P scap; med-submed; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Myrtus communis L. / v-a fo semp Mi P caesp; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Familia PUNICACEAE

Punica granatum L. / v fo dec Mi P caesp; ADV (j.z.az); NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia ONAGRACEAE

Epilobium hirsutum L. / a Mes-Meg H scap; evr-az-(subbor-mer)-afr; NATURA 2000-2190

Ludwigia palustris (L.) Elliott. / a Mes- Mac rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190

Oenothera biennis L. / a Meg-Alt H bienn; ADV (sj. am); NATURA 2000-2120, 2190, 2240

Oenothera fallax Reuner. / a Meg-Alt H bienn; ADV (sj. am); NATURA 2000-2120, 2240

Oenothera glazioviana Micheli / v-a Meg-Alt H bienn; ADV (sj.am); NATURA 2000-2240

Oenothera suaveolens Pers. / a Meg-Alt H bienn; ADV (sj.am); NATURA 2000-2120, 2240, 2190

Familia HALORAGACEAE

Myriophyllum spicatum L. / v-a rad sbm Hyd T; evr-sam; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia THELIGONACEAE

Theligonum cynocrambe L. / v Mes-Meg T scap; stenomed

Familia CORNACEAE

Aucuba japonica Thunb. / a fo semp Mi P scap; ADV (c.az.)

Cornus alba L.* / a fo dec Mi P scap; ADV (sibir); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Cornus mas L. / n-v fo dec Mi P caesp; (i.med)-c.i.submed-j.z.pont-pann-bohem-j.atl; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0, 92A0

Cornus sanguinea L. / n-v fo dec Mi P caesp; (c.med)-z.submed-balk-z.(sr.)pont-sr.sarm-j.atl; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0, 92A0

Familia ARALIACEAE

Hedera helix L. ssp. *euhelix* / aut Alt fo semp S lig; sr.evr.atl-med-submed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia APIACEAE

Anethum graveolens L.* a Meg-Alt H scap; ADV (jz.az); (Adamović L. 1913)

Anthriscus cerefolium (L.) Hoffm.* / v Mes-Mac T scap; ADV (z. az); (Rohlena 1904)

Berula erecta (Hudson) Coville / a Mes-Meg stl rhiz emer Hyd G; se-med-submed-or-pont; NATURA 2000-2190

Bupleurum baldense Turra ssp. *gussonei* (Archangeli) Tutin* / v-a Mes T scap; med-submed-(apen-illyr); (Rohlena 1942)

Bupleurum lancifolium Hornem* / v-a Mi-Mac T scap; med-s.i.iber-illyr; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Bupleurum praealtum L. / a Mi-Mes T scap; c.med-s.j.i.iber-alb-matr; (Horak 1900; Rohlena 1942)

Chaerophyllum coloratum L.* / a Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed-(ilir-jadr); (Rohlena 1904,1942)

Crithmum maritimum L. / v-a Mes-Mac Ch suffr; med-atl

Daucus carota L. / v-a Mac-Meg H semiros bienn; sr.evr-pont-or-tur-i.afri; NATURA 2000-2240

Daucus guttatus Sibth & Sm. / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240

Echinophora spinosa L. / a Mes-Mac H scap; cirk-med; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*;

Sporobolo-elymentum farcti; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120

Eryngium amethystinum L. / a Mes-Mac H scap; c.med-z.aeg-illyr-app

Eryngium maritimum L. / a Mes-Mac G rhiz scap; med-atl; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*;

Sporobolo-elymentum farcti; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120

Foeniculum vulgare Miller / a-aut Meg-Alt H scap; makar-med-i.submed-or-turcest-z.him

Hydrocotyle vulgaris L. / a nat rhiz Hyd G; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2190

Myrrhoides nodosa (L.) Cannon* /v Mes-Meg T scap; stenomed; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942)

Oenanthe aquatica (L.) Poiret in Lam. / a Mes-Alt rhiz emer Hyd T; z.c.evr-az; NATURA 2000-92A0, 2190

Oenanthe fistulosa L. / v Mes-Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; evr; NATURA 2000-2190

Oenanthe pimpinelloides L. / v-a Mes-Meg rhiz emer Hyd G; z.med-anat-submed-j.atl-j.brit

Oenanthe silaifolia Bieb. / a Mes-Alt tub emer Hyd G; sr.evr.-med; NATURA 2000-2190

Opopanax chironium (L.) Koch / a Alt H scap; med-submed

Orlaya grandiflora (L.) Hoffm. / v-a Meg T scap; (med)-s.j.iber-trac-krim-z.matr-z.herc-j.atl

Pimpinella peregrina L. / a Mes H scap bienn; med-submed

Pseudorlaya pumila (L.) Grande / a Mi-Mes T scap; stenomed; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; *Sporobolo-elymentum farcti*; NATURA 2000-2110

Ptychotis verticillata Duby* / v-a Meg T scap; evr; (Adamović L. 1913)

Scandix pecten-veneris L. / v-a Mes-Meg T semiros; c.evr-med-turcest-z.him-submed-atl

Sium latifolium L. / a Meg-Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; evr; NATURA 2000-2190

Smyrniolum olusatrum L.* / v Mac-Meg H scap; v Mac-Meg H scap; (Adamović L. 1913)

Smyrniolum perfoliatum L. / v Mac-Meg H scap; med-submed-pann

Tordylium officinale L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0

Torilis arvensis (Hudson) Link ssp. *arvensis* / v-a Mes T scap; kosm (evr-med)

Familia ERICACEAE

Arbutus unedo L. / fo semp Mi P caesp; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-92A0

Erica arborea L. * / eric semp N-Mi P caesp; evr (med)-afri; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Familia PRIMULACEAE

Anagalis arvensis L. / v-aut Mi T rept; kosm (med)

Anagalis foemina Miller / v-a Mi-Mes T rept; kosm

Asterolinon linum - stellatum (L.) Duby in DC.* / v Mi Tscap; med-submed; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)

Lysimachia atropurpurea L. / a Mes-Meg H scap; med; NATURA 2000-92A0, 2190

Lysimachia nummularia L. / v-a N-Mi Ch herb rept; sr.evr; NATURA 2000-92A0, 2190

Lysimachia vulgaris L. / a Mac-Meg rhiz emer Hyd G; evr-az-(temp-submer); NATURA 2000-2190

Primula vulgaris Hudson / v Mi H ros; cirkhol-(bor-mer); NATURA 2000-92A0

Samolus valerandi L. / a Mi-Mac H scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-1410, 2190, 92A0

Familia PLUMBAGINACEAE

Limonium angustifolium (Tausch) Turrill / aut Mac-Meg H ros; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-1410

Limonium cancellatum (Bernh ex Bertol) O. Kuntze / a Mac-Meg H ros; si.stenomed

Familia OLEACEAE

Forsythia viridissima Lindl. / fo dec Mi P caesp; ADV (i.az.)

Fraxinus angustifolia Vahl. / fo dec Mi P scap; j.atl-med-submed-pann-pont-j.sib; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Fraxinus angustifolia Vahl. ssp. *oxycarpa* (Bieb ex Willd) Franco & Rocha Afonso / v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap; sr.evr-sudsib; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Fraxinus ornus L. / v fo dec Mi-Mes P scap; (j.i.iber-c.i.med)-provans-apen-illyr-sj.z.anat-i.karp-matr; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Jasminum mesnyi Hance* / fo dec Mi P caesp; ADV (i.az); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Jasminum nudiflorum Lindley* / fo dec Mi P caesp; ADV (i.az); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Ligustrum vulgare L. / v-a fo dec Mi P caesp; submed-eux-pann-j.c.evr-subatl-j.atl-j.brit; NATURA 2000-92A0

Olea europaea L. / v fo semp Mi-Mes P scap; med-submed

Olea europaea L. ssp. *europaea* / v fo semp Mi-Mes P scap; med-submed

Phillyrea latifolia L. / v fo semp N-Mi P caesp; stenomed; NATURA 2000-2270*

Familia GENTIANACEAE

Blackstonia perfoliata (L.) Hudson / a Mi-Mes T scap; med-z.c.submed-kolh-atl-j.subatl-(pann); *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2190

Centaurium erythraea Rafn. / v-a Mi-Mes H semiros bienn; sr.evr-med-submed-z.pont-turcest-or; NATURA 2000-2190

Centaurium pulchellum (Swartz) Druce / a-aut Mi-Mes T scap; evr-afr; NATURA 2000-2190

Centaurium spicatum (L.) Fritsch. / a Mi-Mes T scap; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*

Cicendia filiformis (L.) Delarbre / a Mi rhiz emer Hyd T; j.z.evr (subatl); NATURA 2000-3170*

Familia APOCYNACEAE

Nerium oleander L. / v-a fo semp Mi P caesp; ADV (med-i.az)

Vinca major L. / v fo semp Mes-Mac Ch suffr rept; ADV (med-i.az)

Familia ASCLEPIADACEAE

Cionura erecta (L.) Griseb* / v-a Meg-Alt H caesp; med-submed; (Baldacci 1891; Horak 1900; Rohlena 1942)

Cynachum acutum L. / a Mi-Mes fo semp S lig; paleosubtrop; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; NATURA 2000-2110

Periploca graeca L. / v-a fo semp Mes-Alt S lig; i.med-submed; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Vincetoxicum huteri Vis. & Ascherson / v-a Mes H scap; med-submed (illyr (adr)-sr. pind)

Familia CONVULVULACEAE

Calystegia sepium (L.) R. Br. / v-a Alt SH herb; kosm (evr-sam)

Calystegia silvatica (Kit) Griseb / v-a Alt SH herb; med-j.i.iber-kavk; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Calystegia soldanella (L.) R. Br. / a Mi G rhiz; kosm; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120

Convolvulus arvensis L. / v-a SH herb; kosm (med)

Convolvulus canmtabrica L. / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; med-sj.z.iran-submed

Cuscuta australis R. Br. ssp. *cesattiana* (Bertol) Feinbrun / a-aut Alt scand Par; ADV (afr.); NATURA 2000-2270*

Cuscuta campestris Yuncker / a-aut Alt scand Par; ADV (sj. am); *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110

Cuscuta eropaea L. / a-aut Alt scand Par; evr-az; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; NATURA 2000-2110

Ipomoea purpurea Roth. / v-aut Mes-Meg T scap; ADV (c.am.)

Familia BORAGINACEAE

Alkanna tinctoria (L.) Tausch / v Mes H rept; z.pont-i.submed; NATURA 2000-2240, 2190, 2120, 2130*

Anchusa variegata (L.) Lehm. / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; c.i.med-submed

Borago officinalis L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-2240

Buglossoides arvensis (L.) I. M. Johnston* / a Mi - Mes T scap; c.i.med-s.z.iran; (Rohlena 1904)

Buglossoides purpureoerulea (L.) I. M. Johnston / v-a Mac H scap rept; j.evr-med-pont

Cynoglossum creticum Miller. / v Mes-Mac H scap bienn; turcest-med-submed-j.atl; NATURA 2000-92A0

Echium italicum L. / a Mes-Meg H semiros bienn; sr.evr-med-turcest-j.z.pont-(pann)-i.submed;

Echium vulgare L. / v-aut Mes-Meg H semiros bienn; evr-az
Heliotropium eropaeum L. / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed-pann-z.pont
Myosotis arvensis (L.) Hill. / V Mes T scap semiros; evr; NATURA 2000-2190
Myosotis discolor Pers. / V Mes T scap semiros; makar-lusit-z.(c.)med-z.(c.); NATURA 2000-2190
Symphytum tuberosum L. / v Mes-Mac G tub caesp; c.iber-trac-(j.z.pont)-matr-karp-i.herc-j.atl; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia VERBENACEAE

Lippia nodiflora (L.) Michx. / a Mi Ch rept; pantrop; NATURA 2000-2190
Verbena officinalis L. / a-aut Mes-Meg H scap; kosm (evr-s.af); NATURA 2000-2240
Vitex agnus-castus L. / a fo dec NP caesp; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Familia CALLITRICHACEAE

Callitriche hamulata Kutz. ex Koch. / v rad nat Hyd G; cirkhol; NATURA 2000-2190
Callitriche palustris L. / a rad nat Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia LAMIACEAE

Ajuga chamaepitys (L.) Schreber / v-aut Mi-Mes H scap; i.med-anats.z.iran-crim-thrac; NATURA 2000-2240
Ajuga reptans L. / v-a Mes H rept; sr.evr-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Ballota nigra L. / a Meg H scap; j.evr-pont; NATURA 2000-92A0
Calamintha nepeta (L.) Savi ssp. *glandulosa* (Req.) R. W. Ball / a-aut Mes-Mac H scap; z.i.med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Calamintha nepeta (L.) Savi ssp. *nepeta* / a-aut Mes-Mac H scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Lamium amplexicaule L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; evr-az-i.af
Lamium bifidum Cyr. / v Mes-MacT scap; c med-crit-(z.)-c.submed-dac; NATURA 2000-92A0
Lamium purpureum L. / n-aut Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed-pont-sr.evr-(sj.evr); NATURA 2000-92A0
Lamium maculatum L.* / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; sr.evr-submed-j.z.pont; (Rohlena 1904)
Lamium molucellifolium Fries* / v-aut Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; (Adamović L. 1913)
Lycopus europaeus L. / a Mes-Meg H scap/rhiz emer Hyd G; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-2190
Marrubium incanum Desr. in Lam / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; c.med-submed (apen-adr)
Mentha aquatica L. / a-aut Mes-Meg H scap; evr-af; NATURA 2000-2190
Mentha longifolia (L.) Hudson / v-aut Mes-Meg H scap; evr-z.az.-(temp-merid)-af; NATURA 2000-2190
Mentha pulegium L. / a-aut Mi-Meg H scap; evr-af; NATURA 2000-2190
Micromeria graeca Benth.* / v-a Mes-Mac Ch suffr; med-circadr-provenc; (Adamović L. 1913)
Phlomis fruticosa L. / v fo semp NP caesp; med; (Adamović L. 1913)
Prunella laciniata (L.) L. / a Mi-Mes H scap; atl-sr.evr-med-or
Prunella vulgaris L. / a Mi-Mes H scap; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-92A0
Rosmarinus officinalis L. / v-aut fo semp NP caesp; z.c.med-egej-kir-katal-provans
Salvia officinalis L. / v-a Mes-Meg Ch suffr caesp; i.jadr-z.balk-alb
Salvia verbenaca L. / v-aut Mi-Mes H semiros; med-submed-(atl-subatl); NATURA 2000-2270*
Satureja montana L. / a-aut MesCh suffr caesp; JEP (med disj.-z.submed-sj. anat); NATURA 2000-2270*, 2130*
Scutellaria galericulata L. / a-aut Mes-Mac G rhiz scap; cirkumhol (bor-temp); NATURA 2000-2190
Sideritis romana L. ssp. *purpurea* (Talbot ex Bentham) Heywood / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed-(illyr-jadr); NATURA 2000-2130*
Stachys cretica L.* / a Mes-Meg H scap; s.i.med; (Adamović L. 1913)
Stachys cretica L. ssp. *salvifolia* (Ten.) Rech.* / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; s.i.med; (Adamović L. 1913)
Stachys palustris L. / a Mes-Alt H scap; cirkumhol (bor-submerid); NATURA 2000-2190
Stachys spinulosa Sibth & Sm.* / v-a Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed (balk); (Adamović L. 1913)
Teucrium chamaedrys L. / v-aut Mes Ch suffr caesp; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-2130*
Teucrium polium L. / a Mes Ch suffr caesp; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2270*, 2130*, 2240
Teucrium scordium L. / a Mes-Mac H scap; s.lusit-padan-pann-pont-j.sr.sib-c.evr-j.atl; NATURA 2000-2270*
Thymus longicaulis C. Presl. / v-a Mi-Mes Ch suffr rept; c.med-i.submed

Familia SOLANACEAE

Capsicum annuum L. / a Mes-Mac T scap; ADV (sj.am.)
Datura innoxia Miller. / a-aut Mes-Alt T scap; ADV (c.am)
Datura stramonium L. / a-aut Mes-Alt T scap; ADV (sj.am)

Hyoscyamus albus L.* / v-a Mac T scap/H bienn; makar-med-z.c.submed; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)
Lycium eropaeum L. / v-a fo dec NP caesp; med-submed; (Adamović L. 1913)
Physalis alkekengi L. / a Mac H scap; (c.i.med)-hirc-i.submed-sj.iber-(j.atl)-herc-pont
Physalis angulata L. / a-aut Mi-Mes H scap; ADV (am)
Solanum dulcamara L. / a Alt fo dec S lig; evr-med-pont-or-tur; NATURA 2000-2190
Solanum luteum Miller ssp. *alatum* (Moench) in Dostal / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap; med-z.iran-submed-(z.pont)-j.atl-j.c.evr
Solanum melongena L. / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap; ADV (j.i. az.)
Solanum nigrum L. / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap; kosm (evr-sj.am)

Familia SCROPHULARIACEAE

Antirrhinum majus L. ssp. *majus* / a Mes-Alt Ch frut; med-katal-j.burg-cirk-jadr
Bellardia trixago (L.) All. / v Mi-Mac T scap; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2240
Cymbalaria muralis P. Gaertner, B. Meyer & Scherb* / (Rohlena 1902b, 1942); v-a Mi-Mes Ch herb rept; c.evr-z.c.med-z.submed
Gratiola officinalis L. / v-a rhiz emer Hyd G; cirkumhol (subbor-submerid); NATURA 2000-2190
Kickxia cirrhosa (L.) Fritsch. / a Mes-Mac T scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-2240
Kickxia commutata (Bernh. Ex Reichenb) Fritsch. / v-a Mes-Mac T rept; med-submed; (Baldacci 1891; Rohlena 1942)
Kickxia elatine (L.) Dumort* / v-a Mes T rept; sr.evr-med-submed-pont-z.turan; (Rohlena 1902b; Adamović L. 1913)
Linaria genistifolia(L.) Miller ssp. *dalmatica* (L.) Maire & Pettitmening / a Mes-Meg H scap; sr.evr-submed-pont-j.sib; NATURA 2000-2240
Linaria pelisseriana (L.) Miller / v Mes T scap; med-atl
Linaria vulgaris Miller / a-aut Mes-Meg H scap; evr-med-z.az
Melampyrum barbatum Waldst. & Kit. Ex Willd ssp. *carstiense* Ronniger / a-aut Mes-Meg H scap; evr-med-z.az; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)
Odontites verna (Bellardi) Dumort ssp. *verna* / a-aut Mes-Mac T scap; c.evr-atl-submed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0
Parentucellia latifolia (L.) Caruel in Parl. / a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed/z.i.med-submed
Parentucellia viscosa (L.) Caruel in Parl. / a Mi-Mes T scap; evr-med-subatl
Scrophularia nodosa L. / a Meg-Alt H scap; evr-az-(subbor-submedit)
Scrophularia peregrina L. / a Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2190
Verbascum ambigenis Hausskn. / v-a Mac-Alt H semiros; med-submed; (Niketić 2000)
Verbascum blattaria L. / a Meg-Alt H semiros bienn; turcest-med-submed-z.sr.pont+(aralokasp)j.sarm-j.c.evr
Verbascum glabratum Friv. ssp. *brandzae* (Fronachet ex Brandza) Murb.* / a Mes-Meg H scap semiros; med-submed-pont;(Rohlena 1942)
Verbascum glabratum Friv. ssp. *glabratum** / a Mes-Meg H scap semiros; i.JEP (karp-balk); (Rohlena 1902b, 1904)
Verbascum puerulentum Vill.* / v-aut Mac-Alt H semiros bienn; c.med- z.c.submed-j.atl-j.i.brit-burgund-(ren); (Rohlena 1942)
Verbascum sinuatum L. / v-a Mac-Alt H semiros; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240
Veronica acinifolia L.* / v Mi-Mes T scap; (z. med-z.c.submed-j.atl-j.subatl); (Rohlena 1942)
Veronica anagalis-aquatica L. / a-aut Mes-Meg rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm (cirkpol); NATURA 2000-92A0, 2190
Veronica arvensis L. / v N-Mes T scap; kosm (med)
Veronica austriaca L. ssp. *austriaca* / v-a Mi-Meg H scap; j.sarm-pann-i.alp-i.submed-pont; NATURA 2000-92A0
Veronica beccabunga L. / v-a Mes-Mac H rept; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-2190
Veronica chamaedrys L. / v-a Meg H scap; evr-az-(temp-mer); NATURA 2000-92A0
Veronica cymbalaria Bodard* / n-v Mi-Mac T scap; med-submed-balk-krim; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)
Veronica hederifolia L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; sr.evr-submed-pont
Veronica multifida L. / a Mes H rept; evr-az; (Rohlena 1904)
Veronica persica Poiret in Lam. / a-aut Mi-Mes T scap; kosm (med-submed); *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0
Veronica polita Fries. / v Mi-Mes T scap; sr.evr-med-turcest-submed-pont
Veronica serpyllifolia L. / v-aut Mi-Mes H rept; kosm; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia ACANTHACEAE

Acanthus spinosus L.* / v-a Mes-Alt H semiros; c.i.med-submed; (Rohlena 1942; Adamović L. 1913)

Familia OROBANCHACEAE

Orobanche crenata Forskal / v-a Mes-Mac T par; euri-medit-turan; (Rohlena 1902b)

Orobanche ramosa L. ssp. *nana* (Reuter) Continho / v-a Mi-Mes T par; med-submed-pann; NATURA 2000-1410

Familia LENTIBULARIACEAE

Utricularia vulgaris L. / v er sbm Hyd T; evr-sam; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia RUBIACEAE

Asperula arvensis L. / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed-(pann-j.atl)-j.subatl; NATURA 2000-92A0

Crucianella latifolia L. / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; stenomed; (Adamović L.1913)

Cruciata laevipes Opiz. / v-a Mes-Mac H scap; atl-sr.evr-med-submed-or-tur-c.az

Galium aparine L. / v-a Mac-Alt ST herb; evr-az-(bor-mer)

Galium divaricatum Pourret ex Lam. / v-a Mi T scap; stenomed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Galium murale (L.) All. / v Mi-Mes T scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-92A0

Galium palustre L. / v-a Mes-Mac H scap; amf.atl-evr-z.az; NATURA 2000-92A0, 2190

Galium parisiense L. / v-a Mi-Mac T scap; z.c.med-z.submed-balk-(pann)-z.herc-j.atl-j.brit; NATURA 2000-92A0

Putoria calabrica (L. Fil) DC* / a Mi Ch frut; med-submed; (Baldacci 1891; Rohlena 1942)

Rubia peregrina L. / v Alt fo semp S lig; z.med-egej-z.c.submed-j.atl-j.brit; NATURA 2000-2270*

Rubia tinctorum L. / v Alt H scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-2270*

Sherardia arvensis L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; kosm (med); NATURA 2000-92A0

Valantia muralis L.* / v N-Mes T scap; stenomed; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942; Adamović L. 1913)

Familia PLANTAGINACEAE

Plantago arenaria Waldst & Kit. / a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed-(rhen-bohem)-polan-j.z.sarm-pann-pont-aralocasp

Plantago bellardii All. / v-a Mi T ros; med-submed

Plantago coronopus L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed

Plantago lanceolata L. / v-a Mi-Meg H ros; evr-az-(subbor-temp)

Plantago major L. / v-a Mes-Mac H ros; kosm (evr-sj.am); NATURA 2000-92A0

Plantago media L. / v-a Mes-Mac H rose; evr-az

Familia CAPRIFOLIACEAE

Lonicera caprifolium L. / a fo semp S lig; evr; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Lonicera etrusca G. Santi* / v-a Alt fo semp S lig; med-sj.i.iber-provans-(burg)-lig-cirkjadr-mak-z.anat; (Rohlena 1902a, 1942; Martinić et al. 2006)

Lonicera nitida E. H. Wilson.* / fo semp Mi P caesp; ADV (i.az); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Lonicera xylosteum L. / v-a fo dec NP caesp; evr; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Sambucus ebulus L. / a Alt G rad scap/H scap; sr.evr-med-subm-pont-j.sib-or-tur

Sambucus nigra L. / v fo dec Mi P caesp; c.evr-atl-z.(i.) med-subm-(j.z.pont)-pann; NATURA 2000-92A0

Viburnum tinus L. / fo semp N-Mi P caesp; stenomed

Familia BIGNONIACEAE

Campsis radicans (L.) Seem. ex Bureau / a fo dec S lig; ADV (sj.am)

Catalpa bignonioides Walter / v-a fo dec Mes P scap; ADV (j.i.am)

Paulownia tomentosa (Thunb.) Steud.* / v-a fo dec NP caesp; ADV (i.az); (Bunuševac et al. 1977)

Familia VALERIANACEAE

Valerianella dentata (L.) Pollich / v-a Mes T scap; c.evr-j.atl-j.brit-(meddisj.)-submed

Vallerianella discoidea (L.) Loisel / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-2190

Vallerianella locusta (L.) Laterrade / v Mes T semiros; kosm (med); NATURA 2000-2190

Familia DIPSACACEAE

Dipsacus laciniatus L. / a Mac-Alt H bienn; i.med-j.turcest-pont-pann-i.submed-iber-(j.atl- j.c.evr); NATURA 2000-3170*

Knautia arvensis (L.) Coulter / a Mes-Meg H scap; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Knautia integrifolia (L.) Bertol / a Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Knautia purpurea (Vill.) Borbas* / a Mes-MacH; semirosJEP; (Rohlena 1903)

Scabiosa argentea L. / a Mes-Meg H scap/H scap bienn; submed-pont-j.sib.; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0

Succisella inflexa (Kluk.) G. Beck / aut Mes-Meg H scap; j.evr-j.sib; *Robureto - Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia CAMPANULACEAE

- Campanula lingulata* Waldst & Kit. / v-a Mes H scap bienn; sr.evr-med-(karp-balk-pann)
Campanula ramosissima Sibth & Sm.* / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed-(j.alp-illyr-hel-z.egej); (Rohlena 1904)
Campanula rapunculus L. / v-a Mes-Meg H scap bienn; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-92A0
Campanula trachelium L. / a Mes-Meg H semiros; (med-disj.)-sj.i.iber-balk-(pont)-pann-j.brit-subatl-sarm
Legousia speculum-veneris (L.) Chaix in Vil. / v Mi-Mes T scap; sr.evr-med-submed

Familia ASTERACEAE

- Achillea nobilis* L. / a Mes-Mac H semiros; anat-z.iran-pyr-i.submed-illyr-pann-(z.pont); NATURA 2000-92A0
Aetheorhiza bulbosa (L.) Cass / v Mi-Mes G bulb; cirkmed; NATURA 2000-2110
Ambrosia coronopifolia Torrey & A. Gray* / a-aut Mes-Meg G rhiz; ADV (am); (Pulević 1976)
Artemisia campestris L. / a Meg-Alt Ch suffr; cirkumbor; NATURA 2000-2240, 2130*
Artemisia vulgaris L. / a-aut Meg-Alt H scap; cirkhol (subbor-merid); NATURA 2000-2270*
Aster squamatus (Sprengel) Hieron / a-aut Mes-MegT scap; ADV (j.am.)
Aster tripolim L. / a-aut Mes-Alt H scap; evr-az; NATURA 2000-1410, 6420
Asteriscus aquaticus (L.) Les* / a Mi-Mes T scap; stenomed; (Adamović L. 1913)
Bellis perennis L. / v-a Mes H ros; sr.evr-med-submed
Bellis sylvestris Cyr. / aut Mes H ros; med-z.c.submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Bidens frondosa L. / a Mes-Meg T scap; ADV (am); NATURA 2000-3170*
Bidens tripartita L. / a Mac-Meg T scap; evr; NATURA 2000-317*
Bombycilaena erecta (L.) Smolj / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; med-pont-j.sib; (Adamović L. 1913)
Calendula arvensis L. / a-aut Mes-Mac T scap; med-or-z.c.submed-j.atl-j.brit-j.subatl
Calendula officinalis L.* / a Mes-Meg H scap bienn; med; (Baldacci 1910)
Carduus pycnocephalus L. / v-a Mes-Meg T scap; med-i.iber-c.submed-or-j.turcest; NATURA 2000-92A0
Centaurea alba L. / a Mes-Meg H scap bienn; evr-med; NATURA 2000-92A0
Centaurea iberica Trev. ex Sprengel* / a Mes-Meg H scap; i.med-or-turcest-i.submed-transilv; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Centaurea jacea L. / a Meg H scap; evr-az (bor-submer); NATURA 2000-92A0, 2240
Chamomilla recutita (L.) Rauschert / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; kosm;NATURA 2000-2240
Chondrilla juncea L. / a-aut Mac-Alt H scap; med-tur-(j.sib)-pont-submed-j.atl- j.c.evr
Cichorium intybus L. / v-aut Meg-Alt H scap; kosm (evr); NATURA 2000-92A0
Cirsium vulgare (Savi.) Ten. / a Meg-Alt H scap bienn; evr-az (bor-mer)
Conyza albida Willd. ex Spreng / a Meg-Alt T scap; ADV (sj.am); NATURA 2000-2270*
Conyza canadensis (L.) Cronq. / a Meg-Alt T scap; ADV (sj.am)
Coreopsis tinctoria Nutt. / a Mi-Mes H scap; ADV (sj.am.)
Crepis foetida L. / a-aut Mes-Mac H semirosbienn; sr.evr-med-submed- pont-j.sib-or; NATURA 2000-2120, 2130*
Crepis neglecta L. / v-a Mes-Meg T scap; apen-jadr-s.z.anatol
Crepis rubra L.* / v-a Mes T scap; med-submed-orient; (Rohlena 1942; Adamović L. 1913)
Crepis sancta (L.) Babcock / v Mi-Mes T scap; c.i.med-submed-turan; NATURA 2000-2130*
Crepis setosa Haller. / a Mes-Meg T scap; i.pyr-i.submed-j.subatl-pann
Crepis vesicaria L.* / v Mac-Meg H semiros; c.i.med-c.i.submed-aubatl; (Rohlena 1902b; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Crepis zacintha (L.) Babcock / v-a Mes T scap; stenomed
Dittrichia graveolens (L.) W. Greuter / a-aut Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed-turan
Dittrichia viscosa (L.) W. Greuter / a-aut Mac-Alt H scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2190, 2130*, 2240, 1410
Eclipta prostrata (L.) L. / a-aut Mi-Mes rhiz emer Hyd T; evr-az; NATURA 2000-3170*, 2190
Erigeron annuus (L.) Pers. / a-aut Mac-AltH scap; ADV (sj.am)
Eupatorium cannabinum L. / a Meg-Alt H scap; sr.evr-(med)-submed-hirc-pont; NATURA 2000-2190
Evax pygmaea (L.) Brot / v Mi-Mes T rept; stenomed; (Rohlena 1942)
Filago vulgaris Lam. / a Mi-Mes T scap; c.med-egej-submed-hyrc-pann-atl-subatl-j.c.evr
Filago pyramidata L.* / a Mi-Mes T scap; z.e.med-submed-or; (Rohlena 1902a)
Galinsoga parviflora Cav. / a Mes-Mac T scap; ADV (j.am)
Hedypnois cretica (L.) Dum. Courset / v Mi-Mes T scap; z.i.med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
Helianthus annuus L. / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap; ADV (am)
Helianthus tuberosus L. / a-aut Alt G tub; ADV (sj.am)
Helicrysum italicum (Roth) G. Don fill in London / v-a Mac Ch suffr caesp; lusit-(z.)c.med-cipr-c.submed; NATURA

2000-2130*

- Hieracium praealtum* Vill. ex Gachnat ssp. *bauhini* (Besser) Pertunnikov in Syreistschikov* / a Meg H rept; sr.evr; (Rohlena 1902b)
- Hyoseris scabra* L.* / v Mi-Mes T ros; stenomed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
- Hypochoeris radicata* L. / a Mes-Meg H ros; evr-submed-z.az; NATURA 2000-2130*
- Inula crithmoides* L. / a-aut Mac Ch suffr; med-atl; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000- 2110, 1410
- Inula spiraeifolia* L.* / a Mes-Meg H scap; (balk)-z.illyr-ap-j.alp-j.gal; (Adamović L. 1913)
- Leontodon hispidus* L. ssp. *danubialis* (Jacq.) Simonkai* / a Mes-Meg H ros; sr.evr; (Rohlena 1904)
- Leontodon tuberosus* L. / aut-v Mes-Mac H ros/G tub; med-z.(c.)submed-(eux); NATURA 2000-92A0
- Leucanthemum vulgare* Lam. / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; evr-az-(bor-mer)
- Logfia gallica* (L.) Cosson & Germ.* / v Mi-Mes T scap; makar-z.(i.)med-z.submed-(euks)-j.atl-j.brit-j.subatl; (Horak 1900; Rohlena 1902a)
- Onopordum illyricum* L. / a Mes-Alt H bienn/H scap; stenomed
- Pallenis spinosa* (L.) Cass. / v-a Mes T scap; med-submed
- Picris echioides* L. / a Mes-Mac T scap; med-z.med-eux
- Picris hieracioides* L. ssp. *hieracioides* / a-aut Mac-Meg H scap; evr-az
- Pulicaria dysenterica* (L.) Bernh. / a-aut Mes-Meg H scap; med-or-tarkest-submed-pann-atl-subatl-herc; NATURA 2000-2190, 6420
- Pulicaria vulgaris* Gaertner / a Mes-Meg T scap; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2190
- Reichardia picroides* (L.) Rothm / a Mes-Mac H scap; med-submed; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 92A0
- Rhagadiolus stellatus* (L.) Gaertner / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed
- Santolina chamaecyparissus* L. / a fo dec N Mi P caesp; ADV (z.c.med)
- Scolymus hispanicus* L. / a Mes-Alt H scap; med-atl; NATURA 2000-2130*, 2240
- Senecio aquaticus* Hill. ssp. *barbareifolius* (Wimmer & Grab) Walters / a-aut Mes-Mac H scap bienn; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2190
- Senecio vulgaris* L. / a-aut Mes-Meg T scap; kosm
- Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertner* / v-a Mes-Alt H bienn; evr-med-turan; (Adamović L. 1913)
- Sonchus arvensis* L. / v-aut Mes-Meg H ros; evr-sib
- Sonchus asper* (L.) Hill ssp. *asper* / a Mac-Alt T scap/H bienn; evr-sam
- Sonchus asper* (L.) Hill ssp. *glaucescens* (Jordan) Ball. / v-aut Mes-Meg T scap; evr
- Sonchus oleraceus* L. / v-aut Mes-Meg T scap; kosm
- Sonchus palustris* L. / v-aut Mes-Meg H ros; evr-caucas; NATURA 2000-2190
- Tagetes minuta* L. / a Mes-Mac T scap; ADV (j.am.); NATURA 2000-2270*
- Tanacetum cinerariifolium* (Trev.) Schultz Bip. / v-a Mes-Meg Ch suffr caesp; med-submed-(illyr)
- Taraxacum decipiens* Raunk. / a Mes H ros; evr-az; NATURA 2000-92A0
- Taraxacum officinale* Weber in Wiggers / v-aut Mes H ros; evr-az
- Taraxacum palustre* (Lyons) Symons / v Mes H ros; evr-az
- Tragopogon crocifolius* L.* / v-a Mes-Meg H scap; stenomed; (Adamović L. 1913)
- Tragopogon porrifolius* L.* / v-a Mes-Meg H scap bienn; c.i.med-i.submed; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942; Adamović L. 1913)
- Tussilago farfara* L.* / v Mi-Mes G rhiz caesp; sr.evr-med-submed-pont-j.sib-c.az; (Rohlena 1904)
- Tyrimnus leucographus* (L.) Cass.* / v-a Mes-Meg T scap; med-submed; (Adamović L. 1913)
- Urospermum picroides* (L.) Scop. ex F. W. Schmidt / n-a Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed
- Xanthium strumarium* L. ssp. *italicum* (Moretti) D.Love / a Meg-Alt T scap; kosm (med); *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120

Classis MONOCOTYLEDONES

Familia ALISMATACEAE

- Alisma plantago-aquatica* L. / a Mes-Meg tub emer Hyd G; cirkhol; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*
- Baldellia ranunculoides* (L.) Parl / a Mi-Mes rhiz emer Hyd G; stenomed-atl; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*
- Sagittaria sagittifolia* L. / a Mes-Meg tub emer Hyd G; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*

Familia BUTOMACEAE

- Butomus umbellatus* L. / v-a Meg-Alt tub emer Hyd G; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia HYDROCHARITACEAE

- Elodea canadensis* Michx. / a rad sbm Hyd T; ADV (sj.am.)
Vallisneria spiralis L. / a rhiz sbm Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia POTAMOGETONACEAE

- Potamogeton crispus* L. / a rhiz sbm Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190
Potamogeton nodosus Poiret in Lam. / v - a rad nat sbm Hyd G, kosm; NATURA 2000-2190
Potamogeton pectinatus L. / a rhiz sbm Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190
Potamogeton perfoliatus L. / a rhiz sbm Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190
Potamogeton pusillus L. / a rhiz sbm Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia POSIDONIACEAE

- Posidonia oceanica* (L.) Delile / a rad sbm Hyd T; stenomed

Familia ZANNICHELLIACEAE

- Zannichellia palustris* L. / a rad sbm Hyd T; kosm

Familia NAJADACEAE

- Najas marina* L. / a rad sbm Hyd T; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190
Najas minor All. / a rad sbm Hyd T; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia LILIACEAE

- Allium chamaemoly* L.* / n Mi-Mes G bulb; stenomed; (Baldacci 1910; Rohlena 1942)
Allium guttatum Steven ssp. *sardoum* (Moris) Stearn / a Mes-Meg G bulb; med-submed
Allium roseum L. / v Mac G bulb; med-submed, NATURA 2000-92A0
Allium spaerocephalon L. / a Mes-Mac G bulb; med-(or)-pann-pont-j.subatl-j.c.ev
Asparagus acutifolius L. / a fo semp S lig; z.i.med-submed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-2270*, 92A0, 2130*
Asphodelus aestivus Brut / v Mac-Meg G rhiz-tub; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*, 2240, 92A0
Asphodeline lutea (L.) Reichenb / Mac-Meg G rhiz-tub; c.i.med-submed
Bellevalia romana (L.) Reichenb. / v Mes-Mac G bulb; med
Colchicum autumnale L. / aut Mi-Mes G bulb; j.ce-z.c.submed-aquit-sr.brit; NATURA 2000-2270*
Colchicum cupanii Guss. ssp. *glosophyllum* (Heldr.) Rouy / aut Mi-Mes G bulb; stenomedit; NATURA 2000-2270*
Colchicum hungaricum Janka* / n Mi-Mes G bulb; illyr-sr.pind-mez; (Rohlena 1942)
Erythronium dens - canis L.* / v Mi-Mes G bulb; evr-az; (Baldacci 1900; Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Hyacinthus orientalis L. / v Mes-Mac G bulb; i.med
Muscari commutatum Guss. / v Mes G bulb; stenomed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Muscari comosum (L.) Miller / v-a Mes-Meg G bulb; med-submed-(or)-pann-j.atl-j.c.evr
Muscari neglectum Guss. ex Ten / v Mes G bulb; (j.subatl)-j.atl-med-submed-pann; NATURA 2000-92A0
Ornithogalum commosum L. / v Mi-Mes G bulb; medit-mont, NATURA 2000-2270*
Ornithogalum exscapum Ten. / v Mi G bulb; med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Ruscus acuelatus L. / v Mes-Meg Ch frut/G rhiz; subatl-z.i.med-submed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0
Scilla autumnalis L. / a-aut Mes G bulb; med-submed-(subatl); NATURA 2000-92A0
Scilla bifolia L. / v-a Mi-Mes G bulb; evr-med-z.az
Smilax aspera L. / a-aut fo semp S lig; med-submed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-2270*, 2130*, 92A0

Familia AGAVACEAE

- Agave americana* L. / a fo dec Mi-Mes P caesp; ADV (sj.am)
Yucca gloriosa L. / a fo dec Mi-Mes P caesp; ADV (j.i.am.)

Familia AMARYLLIDACEAE

- Galanthus nivalis* L. / v Mes-Meg G bulb; evr-med-z.az
Leucojum aestivum L. / v Mes-Meg tub emer Hyd G; c.i.submed-pann-(j.atl-j.ce.disj); NATURA 2000-92A0
Narcissus tazetta L. / v Mes-Meg G bulb; z.i.med-submed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0
Pancratium maritimum L. / a Mac G bulb; cirk-med; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; *Sporobolo-elymentum farcti*; NATURA 2000-2110

Familia DIOSCOREACEAE

Tamus communis L. / v Alt rhiz SG herb; atl-sr.evr-med-submed-or; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia IRIDACEAE

Crocus dalmaticus Vis.* / a Mi G bulb; c.med-submed (illyr-jadr-end); (Blečić&Pulević 1979)

Crocus tommasinianus Herbert* / a Mi G bulb; c.med-submed (illyr-balk-dac-adr); (Baldacci 1910; Rohlena 1942)

Gladiolus imbricatus L. / v Mes G bulb; j.i.evr; NATURA 2000-2270*

Gladiolus palustris Gaudi / a Mes-Mac G bulb; sr.evr; (Adamović R. Ž. 1968)

Hermodactylus tuberosus (L.) Miller* / v Mes-Mac G rhiz; c.i.med-submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)

Iris germanica L. var. *florentina* Dykes / v Mes-Alt G rhiz caesp; med-app

Iris pallida Lam. / v Mes-Alt G rhiz caesp; med-submed (balk-apen)

Iris pseudacorus L. / v-a Mac-Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; med-submed-pont-sr.evr-(j.skand)

Romulea bulbocodium (L.) Sebastiani & Mauri / v Mi-Mes G bulb; stenomed; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia JUNCACEAE

Juncus acutiflorus Ehrh. Ex Hoffm.* / a Mes-Meg G rhiz caesp; evr; (Rohlena 1902b)

Juncus acutus L. / a Mac-Alt H caesp; kosm (med); NATURA 2000-1410, 6420

Juncus anceps Laharpe / v-a Mes-Mac G rhiz caesp; z.med-atl; NATURA 2000-1410, 6420

Juncus articulatus L. / a Mes-Meg rhiz emer Hyd G; amfiatl-s.am-evr-az; NATURA 2000-1410, 6420

Juncus bufonius L. / a Mi-Mes rhiz emer Hyd T; kosm; NATURA 2000-1410, 3170*

Juncus capitatus Weigel. / v Mi-Mes T scap; evr-(temp-mer)-afr-(trop-austr); NATURA 2000-1410, 3170*

Juncus compressus Weigel. / a Mi-Mes rhiz emer Hyd T; evr-az; NATURA 2000-1410, 6420

Juncus gerardi Loisel in Desv / a Mes-Macrhiz emer Hyd T; cirkhol; NATURA 2000-1410, 6420

Juncus maritimus Lam. / a Mac-Meg G rhiz; kosm (med); *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 1410, 6420

Juncus pygmaeus L. C. M. Richard in Thuill / a Mi-Mes T caesp; evr-med-subatl; NATURA 2000-1410

Luzula campestris (L.) DC. / a Mes H caesp; evr; NATURA 2000-92A0

Luzula forsteri (Sm.) DC. in Lam. & DC. / v Mes-Mac H caesp; evr-z.az-s.am-(temp-merid); NATURA 2000-92A0

Luzula multiflora (Retz.) Lej. / a Mes H caesp; kosm; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia COMMELINACEAE

Commelina communis L. / a Mac-Meg G bulb rept; ADV (i.-j.i.az)

Familia POACEAE

Aegilops neglecta Req. ex Bertol / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-tur; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2130*

Agrostis stolonifera L. / v-a Mes-Mac H rept; kosm (evr); NATURA 2000-6420

Aira elegantissima Schur. / a Mes T scap; z.i.med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*

Alopecurus creticus Trin in Sprengel / a Mes-Mac T scap; z.hel-aeg-s.anat; NATURA 2000-6420

Alopecurus utriculatus Solander in A. Russell / v Mes T caesp; submed-jadr; NATURA 2000-92A0

Ammophila arenaria (L.) Link / a Mes-Mac G rhiz; evr-med; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; *Sporobolo-elymentum farcti*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120

Anthoxanthum odoratum L. / a Mes-Meg H caesp; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2130*

Arrhenatherum eliatum (L.) Beauv ex J. & C. Presl* / v Meg-Alt H caesp; z.med-submed-atl-z.(i.)-sarm; (Adamović L. 1913)

Arundo donax L. / a-aut Alt G rhiz; cirk-med; NATURA 2000-2110, 1410

Arundo plinii Turra / a-aut Alt G rhiz; med

Avena barbata Pott. Ex Link in Schreder / v Mes-Meg T scap; med-makar-or-j.atl

Avena sterilis L. / v-a Mes-Meg T scap; med-turan; NATURA 2000-2240

Beckmannia euriciformis (L.) Host. / a Mes-Mac G rhiz; evr-sib

Brachypodium distachyon (L.) Beauv / a Mi-Mes T scap; med-tur

Brachypodium retusum (Pers) Beauv / a Mes-Mac H caesp; z.i.med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240

Brachypodium sylvaticum (Hudson) Beauv / a Mac H caesp; sr.evr-z.med-submed-turcest-altai; NATURA 2000-2240

Briza maxima L. / a Mes-Meg T scap; kosm (med-submed); NATURA 2000-1410, 6420, 92A0

Briza minor L. / v Mi-Mes T scap; kosm (med-submed); NATURA 2000-1410, 6420, 92A0

Bromus arvensis L.* / a Mes-Meg T scap; evr-az; (Rohlena 1942)

Bromus commutatus Schrader* / v Mac-Meg T scap; c.evr-z.submed-subatl; (Rohlena 1902b)

Bromus diandrus Roth. / a Mes-Mac T scap; eurimed

Bromus erectus Hudson / a Mac H caesp; c.evr-med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240

- Bromus hordaceus* L. ssp. *hordaceus* / a Mes T scap; kosm; NATURA 2000-2240, 92A0
- Bromus madritens* L. / a Mes-Mac T scap; macar-med-or-j.atl
- Bromus rigidus* Roth. / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240
- Bromus squarrosus* L. ssp. *squarrosus** / v Mes-Mac T scap; med-tur-submed-pont-pann; (Rohlena 1942)
- Bromus sterilis* L. / a Mes-Meg T caesp; cirkumhol
- Bromus tectorum* L. / a Mes-Mac T scap; paleotemp; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110
- Cenchrus incertus* M. A. Curtis / A Mes T scap; ADV (j.am.)
- Chrysopogon gryllus* (L.) Trin. / a Alt H caesp; med-i.c.submed-pann; NATURA 2000-2240
- Corynephorus canescens* (L.) Beauv. / a Mes H caesp; z.evr (subatl); NATURA 2000-2130*
- Crypsis acuelata* (L.) Aiton / a-aut Mi-Mac Tscap; subtrop; NATURA 2000-1410
- Crypsis alopecuroides* (Piller & Mitterp) Schrader / a-aut Mi-Mac Tscap; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-3170*
- Crypsis schoenoides* (L.) Lam. / a-aut Mi-Mac Tscap; med-or.tur-j.atl-pont-pann-j.atl; NATURA 2000-3170*
- Cutandia maritima* (L.) W. Barbey / a Mi-Mes T scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120, 2220, 2130*, 2190
- Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. / a-aut Mes G rhiz rept caesp; kosm (med-or-tur)
- Cynosurus cristatus* L. / A Mes-Mac H caesp; med-atl; NATURA 2000-92A0
- Cynosurus echinatus* L.* / v-a Mes-Mac T scap; macar-med-submed-(subatl-brit); (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)
- Dactylis glomerata* L. ssp. *glomerata* / a Meg H caesp; evr-az; NATURA 2000-2240
- Dactylis glomerata* L. ssp. *hispanica* (Roth) Nyman* / v-a Mes-Mac H scap; med-(or)-submed; (Adamović L. 1913)
- Dasypyrum villosum* (L.) P. Candargy / a Mes-Meg T scap; med-pont; NATURA 2000-2240
- Desmazeria marina* (L.) Druce / v Mi-Mes T scap; med-atl
- Desmazeria rigida* (L.) Tutin / a Mi-Mes T caesp; makar-med-submed-arm-j.atl-brit
- Dichanthium ischaemum* (L.) Roberty / a Mes-Mac H caesp; kosm
- Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop / a Mes T caesp rept; kosm (evr-sam)
- Echinochloa crus-gali* (Live.) Beauv / a-aut Mac-Alt T scap; kosm (subtrop-trop); NATURA 2000-2190
- Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertner / a Mes T scap; ADV (afr)
- Eleusine tristachya* (Lam.) Lam. / A Mes T scap; ADV (afr)
- Elymus farctus* (Viv.) Runemark ex Melderis / a Mac G rhiz; cirk-med; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; *Sporobolo-elymentum farcti*; NATURA 2000-2110
- Elymus pungens* (Pers.) Melderis* / a Mac G rhiz; eurimed; (Adamović L. 1913)
- Eragrostis pilosa* (L.) Beauv* / a-aut Mi-Mes Tscap; kosm; (Adamović L. 1913)
- Festuca arundinacea* Schreber / v-a Meg H caesp; z.c.submed-pann-atl-subatl-balt
- Festuca pratensis* Hudson. / v-a Mes-Mac Hcaesp; evr-az
- Festuca vallesiaca* Schleicher ex Gaudin / a Mi-Mes H caesp; i.submed-turcest-aralokasp-sr.sib-pont-j.sarm-herc-c.alp; NATURA 2000-2240
- Gastridium ventricosum* (Gouan) Schinz & Thell. / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; abes-macar-med-(j. atl)
- Gaudinia fragilis* (L.) Beauv / a Mes-Meg T scap; evr-med
- Hainardia cylindrica* (Willd) W. Greuter / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed, *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110
- Holcus lanatus* L. / v-a Meg H scap; z.c.med-submed-atl-z(i).sarm
- Hordeum marinum* Hudson* / v Mi-Mes T scap; cirkumhol; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
- Hordeum murinum* L. ssp. *leporinum* (Link) Archangeli / v Mes-Meg T caesp; kosm; NATURA 2000-2240
- Imperata cylindrica* (L.) Rauschel / a Mac-Meg G rhiz caesp; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120
- Lagurus ovatus* L. / v N Mac T scap; (macar)-med-z.submed-(j.atl); *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2240
- Lolium multiflorum* Lam. / v-a Mes-Mac H caesp; kosm (med); NATURA 2000-2240
- Lolium rigidum* Gaudin ssp. *lepturoides* (Boiss.) Sennen & Mauricio / v-a Mi-Mes T scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2130*
- Lolium temulentum* L.* / v Mes-MegH scap; kosm (med); (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)
- Lophochloa cristata* (L.) Hyl. / v-a Mi-Mac T caesp; atl-med
- Melica ciliata* L. / a Mes-Meg H caesp; evr-med-z.az
- Melica uniflora* Retz.* / v-a Mes-Meg H caesp; c.evr-atl-submed; (Rohlena 1942)
- Parapholis incurva* (L.) CE. Hubbard / a Mi-Mes T scap; med-atl; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110
- Paspalum dilatatum* Poirlet in Lam. / a Mac-Meg H caesp; ADV (j.am.)
- Paspalum paspalodes* (Michx) Scribner / a Mi-Mac stl emer Hyd G; ADV (c.am.j.am); NATURA 2000-2190

- Phalaris minor* Retz.* / a Mi-Mes T scap; paleosubtrop; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942)
Phleum arenarium L. / a Mi-Mes T scap; (med)-z.submed-atl-subatl-z.balt; (Rohlena 1902b, 1942; Adamović R. Ž. 1968)
Phleum pratense L. / A Mes-Meg H caesp; sr.evr; NATURA 2000-1410, 2190
Phragmites australis (Cav.) Trin ex Steudel / A Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm (evr-sam); NATURA 2000-2190
Piptatherum miliaceum (L.) Cosson / a Mac-Alt H caesp; macar-med-provens-adr-or; NATURA 2000-92A0
Poa annua L.* / a Mi-Mes T caesp; kosm; (Baldacci 1910; Rohlena 1911, 1942)
Poa bulbosa L. / a Mes-Meg H caesp; sr.evr-med-or-tur-j.sib-pont-c.az; NATURA 2000-2240
Poa jubata A. Kerner* / a Mes-Meg H caesp; evr-az; (Rohlena 1942)
Poa trivialis L. / a Mi-MegH caesp; kosm
Poa trivialis L. ssp. *syvicola* (Guss.) H. Lindb / a Mes-Meg H caesp; evr-az;
Polypogon maritimus Willd. / v Mes T scap; med-atl; NATURA 2000-6420, 2190
Polypogon monspeliensis (L.) Desf. / v Mes-Mac T scap; j.evr-med; NATURA 2000-6420, 2190
Polypogon viridis (Gouan) Breistr* / a Mes-Meg H caesp; evr-med-z.az; (Adamović L. 1913)
Psilurus incurvus (Gouan) Schinz & Thell / v Mes T scap; kosm (evr-sam); NATURA 2000-2240
Puccinellia distans (L.) Parl* / aMac-Alt H caesp; paleotemp; (Adamović L. 1913)
Saccharum ravennae (L.) Murray / a-aut Alt H caesp; med-tur; NATURA 2000-2190, 1410
Sesleria autumnalis (Scop.) F. W. Schultz / a Mes-Meg H caesp; med-submed; (Bunuševac 1977)
Setaria viridis (L.) Beauv. / a-aut Mes-Mac T scap; kosm (evr-sam)
Sorghum halepense (L.) Pers. / a-aut Meg-Alt G rhiz caesp; ADV (paleotrop: i.-afr-j.z.az)
Sporobolus indicus (L.) R. Br. / a Mac-Meg H caesp; ADV (j.am.)
Sporobolus pungens (Schreber) Kunth / a Mes-Mac G rhiz; subtrop; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; *Sporobolo-elymentum farcti*; NATURA 2000-2110
Stipa bromoides (L.) Dorfler / a Meg-Alt H caesp; med-provans-lig-jadr-i.kavk; NATURA 2000-2240
Stipa capensis Thumb / a Mes-Mac T scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-2240
Tragus racemosus (L.) All. / a-aut Mi-Mes T caesp, kosm (evr-afr)
Vulpia bromoides (L.) S. F. Gray / v Mes T caesp; evr-afr
Vulpia ciliata Dumort / v-a Mes-Meg T caesp; j.atl-med-submed-or; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110
Vulpia fasciculata (Forsk.) Samp / v-a Mi-Mes T caesp; med-atl
Vulpia myuros (L.) C. C. Gmelin / a Mes-Meg T caesp; kosm (med-submed); *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110

Familia ARECACEAE

- Chamaerops humillis* L.* / a fo semp N-Mi P scap; stenomed; (Bunuševac et al. 1977)
Chamaerops excelsa Thunb. / a fo semp N-Mi P scap; ADV (i.az)
Washingtonia filifera (J. A. Lindden) H. A. Wendl. / a fo semp Mes P scap; ADV (am)

Familia ARACEAE

- Arum italicum* Miller. / v Mac-Meg G rhiz; med-submed; *Robureto-Carpinetum orientalis*; NATURA 2000-92A0
Arum maculatum L. / v Mes-Meg G rhiz; atl-med-subm-pann-herc; NATURA 2000-92A0

Familia LEMNACEAE

- Lemna minor* L. / a er nat Hyd T; kosm

Familia SPARGANIACEAE

- Sparganium erectum* L. / a Meg rhiz emer Hyd G; evr; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia TYPHACEAE

- Typha angustifolia* L. / a Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190
Typha latifolia L. / a Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190

Familia CYPERACEAE

- Carex acuta* L. / v-a Mes-Mac rhiz emer Hyd G; evr
Carex acutiformis Ehrh.* / v-a Mes-Alt G rhiz; evr-az; (Rohlena 1904)
Carex caryophyllea Latourr / v Meg-Alt G rhiz caesp; evr-med-z.az
Carex distachya Desf. / v Mi-Mes H caesp; med-submed; NATURA 2000-1410
Carex distans L. / v Mes-Meg rhiz emer Hyd G; med-pann-(z.pont)-atl-c.evr; NATURA 2000-1410
Carex divisa Hudson / v Mi-Mes G rhiz caesp; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-1410

- Carex divulsa* Stokes in With / v Mes-Mac G rhiz caesp; makar-med-(or)-submed-pann-(atl-c.evr); NATURA 2000-1410, 2190
Carex extensa Good. / a Mes-Mac H caesp; evr-afr; NATURA 2000-1410
Carex flacca Schreber ssp. *flacca* / v-a Mes-Mac G rhiz caesp; c.evr-(sarm)-med-or-pann-atl; NATURA 2000-2190
Carex halleriana Asso.* / v Mes-Mac G rhiz caesp; med-submed-hirc-(j.subatl); (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Carex olbiensis Jordan* / v Mi-Mes H caesp; stenomed; (Rohlena 1904)
Carex pendula Hudson* / v Mac-Alt H caesp; c.evr-atl-eux-z.med-z.c.submed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Carex remota L. / v-a Mes-Mac H caesp; z.sarm-atl-submed-(z.c.med); NATURA 2000-92A0
Carex riparia Curtis / v-a Mac-Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; cirkumhol
Carex tomentosa L.* / v Mes-Meg G rhiz caesp; z.i.submed-(pont)-j.sib-subatl-sarm; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Carex vulpina L. / v-a Mes-Mac rhiz emer Hyd G; sr.evr-med-turcest-pont-j.sr.sib; NATURA 2000-1410, 2190, 6420
Cladium mariscus (L.) Pohl. / a Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190
Cyperus alternifolius L. / a-aut Mac G rhiz; ADV (j.afr.)
Cyperus capitatus Vandelli / v-a Mes-Mac G rhiz; stenomed; *Xanthio-Cakiletum maritimae*; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; *Sporobolo-elymentum farcti*; NATURA 2000-2110, 2120
Cyperus eragrostis Lam. / a-aut Mes-Mac G rhiz; ADV (j.am.); NATURA 2000-2190
Cyperus flavescens L. / a-aut Mi-Mes T caesp; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*
Cyperus fuscus Lam. / a Mi-Mes emer Hyd T; evr; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*
Cyperus longus L. / v-a Mac rhiz emer Hyd G; evr-afr; NATURA 2000-2190
Cyperus michelianus (L.) Lam. / a Mi-Mes emer Hyd T; paleosubtrop; NATURA 2000-3170*
Cyperus rotundus L. / a-aut Mes G rhiz; kosm
Eleocharis acicularis (L.) Roemer & Schultes / a Mi rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*
Eleocharis palustris (L.) Roemer & Schultes / a Mes-Mac rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-2190, 3170*
Fimbristylis bisumbellata (Forsk.) Bubani / a Mi-Mes emer Hyd T; evr-afr; NATURA 2000-3170*
Schoenus nigricans L. / v-a Mes-Mac H scap; kosm; *Agropyretum mediterraneum*; NATURA 2000-2110, 6420
Scirpus holoschoenus L. / v-a Meg-Alt G rhiz caesp; med-atl-tur-pont-pann; NATURA 2000-6420, 1410
Scirpus lacustris L. / a Alt rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-3170*
Scirpus maritimus L. ssp. *maritimus* / a Mes-Mac rhiz emer Hyd G; kosm; NATURA 2000-3170*
Scirpus setaceus L. / a Mi-Mes emer Hyd T; evr-afr; NATURA 2000-3170*

Familia CANNACEAE

- Canna indica* L. / a fo semp Mi P scap; ADV (j.am)

Familia ORCHIDACEAE

- Anacamptis pyramidalis* (L.) L. C. M. Richard / a Mes-Meg G rhiz scap; atl-med-submed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Ophrys apifera Hudson / v Meg G tub scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240, 92A0
Ophrys bertolonii Moretti. / v Meg G tub scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-2240
Ophrys fusca Link & Schrader* / v Mes G bulb; stenomed; (Rohlena 1904, 1942)
Ophrys scolopax Cav. ssp. *cornuta* (Steven) Camus* / v Meg G tub scap; subeux; (Rohlena 1902b)
Ophrys sphegodes Miller. / v Meg G tub scap; med-submed-j.atl-j.subatl-z.pann; NATURA 2000-92A0
Orchis coriophora L. / v Mes G tub scap; sr.evr-med-submed-j.z.az; NATURA 2000-2240, 92A0
Orchis italica Poiret in Lam.* / v Mes-Mac G bulb; stenomed; (Rohlena 1942)
Orchis laxiflora Lam. / v Mes G tub scap; evr-med-z.az; NATURA 2000-6420, 1410
Orchis laxiflora Lam. ssp. *palustris* (Jacq.) Bonnier & Layers / v Mes G bulb; evr-med; NATURA 2000-6420, 1410
Orchis morio L. ssp. *morio* / v Mi-Mes G tub scap; evr-med-z.az
Orchis papilionacea L.* / v Mes G tub scap; med-submed; (Parolly 1991)
Orchis spitzelii Sauter ex Koch* / v-a Mes G tub; JEP; (Rohlena 1942)
Serapias cordigera L. / v-a Mes-Mac G tub scap; stenomed; NATURA 2000-92A0
Serapias lingua L. / v Mes G tub scap; med; NATURA 2000-6420, 1410, 92A0
Serapias vomeracea (Burm) Briq. / v-a Mes-Mac G tub scap; med-submed; NATURA 2000-6420, 1410, 92A0
Spiranthes spiralis (L.) Chevall. / aut Mi-Mes G tub scap; (med)-submed-akvit-brit-subatl-j.c.evr; NATURA 2000-2270*